

Recommendations for Decolonising Access to Heritage Infrastructures in the Netherlands: An Ethnographic Approach

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Executive Summary

This report presents targeted recommendations for decolonising access to heritage and research infrastructures in the Netherlands, with a specific focus on the GLOBALISE project's digitisation of the VOC archives. Drawing from expert interviews and ethnographic research, these recommendations aim to address the complexities of colonial legacies within Dutch cultural institutions and propose strategies for creating more equitable, inclusive, and emotionally accessible archival spaces. Findings reveal that successful decolonisation requires both technical solutions and fundamental reimagining of institutional relationships with source communities.

Introduction

The GLOBALISE project's digitisation of five million pages from the Dutch East India Company (VOC) archives—processed through advanced handwritten text recognition technology—represents a significant development in archival accessibility. These documents—products of colonial conquest and commerce—contain countless stories, some celebrated, while others deliberately silenced through erasure and violence.

As this research infrastructure prepares to launch globally, we bear a critical responsibility: ensuring that descendants of those documented—often without consent and through colonial perspectives—can engage with these materials with dignity, agency, and emotional safety. This is particularly important given that most categories appearing in these archives were ascribed to individuals by the VOC rather than reflecting self-identification, and are often intricately linked to histories of colonial violence, enslavement, and racism.

Drawing on ethnographic research and extensive interviews with archivists, historians, artists, curators, and technology specialists—from both the Global North and South—representing diverse backgrounds and expertise, this report offers recommendations and pathways to transform colonial archives into a space where multiple perspectives can flourish, where difficult histories can be confronted with appropriate support, and where communities can reclaim narratives that were once written without them.

The recommendations are structured around five key areas, creating a deliberate progression from institutional foundations to sustained impact:

1. **Institutional frameworks** establish ethical principles and team structures
2. **User-centred design** prioritises diverse access needs and emotional safety

3. **Community engagement** transfers interpretive authority to source communities
4. **Technical infrastructure** implements decolonial values in digital systems
5. **Sustainability frameworks** ensure ongoing evaluation and institutional accountability

While these recommendations prioritise digital strategies appropriate to GLOBALISE's nature as an online infrastructure, they acknowledge the value of complementary offline approaches in enhancing engagement with these sensitive materials.

This endeavour extends beyond technical considerations to address fundamental human concerns. As one artist working with the colonial archives explained:

My project in the archive is about bringing people to cry, because we haven't made the proper mourning of this era. And we just keep going as if it was nothing but there is a lot of pain behind them. Still, we can feel it these days. For me, it was important to mobilise these feelings in order to change the perception we have on colonization.¹

Colonial archives thus cannot be treated as mere historical repositories; they actively continue to shape contemporary emotional and lived experiences. Recognising this ongoing impact situates decolonising work as not optional but as an ethical imperative, requiring urgent and sustained commitment.

Implementation Framework

Given resource constraints and implementation complexities, this report includes a strategic prioritisation framework to guide implementation decisions. The framework organises recommendations into three tiers based on implementation complexity, resource requirements, immediate impact potential, and alignment with current organisational capabilities:

- Tier 1 (High Priority): Low to moderate resource requirements, high impact, technically feasible for immediate implementation.
- Tier 2 (Moderate Priority): Moderate to high resource requirements, high impact, requiring careful planning and phased implementation.
- Tier 3 (Lower Priority): High resource requirements or institutional dependencies, excellent for long-term development or strategic partnerships.

Each recommendation includes an assessment based on:

- Resource Level: Financial and human resource requirements
- Implementation Complexity: Technical difficulty and coordination needs
- Impact Potential: Immediate user benefit and transformation potential
- Rationale: Alignment with current capabilities and constraints

¹ Interview, Archives Decolonisation Project, 2024-25

This framework enables strategic decision-making while maintaining the transformative vision of decolonising archival access.

Recommendations

1. Foundational Institutional Frameworks

1.1 Explicit Acknowledgment of Archival Biases

Recommendation: Develop clear, accessible statements about the biases inherent in the archives.

Rationale: Users require context to understand what they are encountering in archives. The VOC archives were created through colonial perspectives, using language and categories that reflected Dutch interests and worldviews. As one expert noted,

Every single archive is biased—whether you like it or not, whether it is colonial or not—but particularly colonial archives tend to suffer more acutely...of particular types of biases. So, whether these are gender, racial, age related, obviously, social class also. There are quite a lot of biases in terms also of what are the voices that can be recorded in colonial archives.²

Being transparent about these biases is an essential first step in decolonising access.

Implementation:

- Create a "Collection Bias Statement", using accessible language, detailing the social, cultural, and historical contexts in which materials were collected
- Develop an introductory module for first-time users
- Design contextual information panels that can be toggled on/off as users navigate the archives
- Produce video interviews with experts discussing the nature of colonial record-keeping
- Provide critical reading guides for colonial documents
- Update statements regularly based on ongoing research and feedback

Priority Assessment:

- Tier: 1 (High Priority)
- Resource Level: LOW
- Implementation Complexity: LOW
- Impact: HIGH
- Rationale: Requires content creation rather than technical development. GLOBALISE has already demonstrated strong competency in this area and can build upon

² Interview, Archives Decolonisation Project, 2024-25

existing foundations with existing team to provide immediate user protection.
Essential foundation for all other decolonisation efforts.

1.2 Socio-Technical Systems Approach

Recommendation: Conceptualise digital archives as "socio-technical machines"³ that require attention to both technological and social dimensions.

Rationale: The danger lies in focusing solely on technical solutions without considering the users. As one expert explained:

We need to think about this problem as socio-technical machines... you might have the most advanced engines, but if you haven't thought about who is going to use the thing, right? Or why people might be interested in this or that, then you might run into problems.⁴

Implementation:

- Conduct user research before implementing technical solutions
- Develop frameworks for evaluating both social and technical impacts of archival initiatives
- Include representatives from impacted communities as paid consultants in design processes
- Design flexible systems that present content differently based on audience needs and relationships to the material
- Document how technical choices affect representation of colonial histories and how they may reinforce or challenge colonial perspectives

Priority Assessment:

- Tier: 3 (Lower Priority)
- Resource Level: HIGH
- Implementation Complexity: HIGH
- Impact: MODERATE-HIGH
- Rationale: Requires fundamental platform redesign and sustained community partnerships. Better suited for major platform revision or long-term institutional development partnerships.

1.3 Diverse Team Composition

Recommendation: Build and maintain diverse teams that include people at various career stages, from different cultural backgrounds, and particularly from communities represented in the archives.

Rationale: Team diversity is crucial for challenging dominant narratives and bringing multiple perspectives to archival work. As an expert emphasised: "One of the things that I think about

³ Interview, Archives Decolonisation Project, 2024-25

⁴ Interview, Archives Decolonisation Project, 2024-25

in team building is that it's not only necessary to have people that are experts... But also to have people in all stages of career and people that do not necessarily belong to Academia."⁵

Implementation:

- Develop hiring practices that prioritise diversity and inclusion
- Create positions specifically for community experts and knowledge holders
- Include non-academic perspectives and expertise in project design and implementation
- Establish community advisory boards with decision-making power
- Build multi-year engagement strategies rather than project-based consultations
- Establish fair compensation for community experts and knowledge holders
- Create pathways for career progression within the institution
- Provide cultural competency training for all staff members

Priority Assessment:

- Tier: 1 (High Priority)
- Resource Level: MODERATE
- Implementation Complexity: LOW-MODERATE
- Impact: HIGH
- Rationale: Essential to authentic decolonisation—without diverse perspectives, efforts risk reproducing colonial power dynamics. GLOBALISE has already built a diverse team and can further leverage this foundation to further strengthen community representation.

2. User-Centered Design and Accessibility

2.1 User Research and Audience Analysis

Recommendation: Conduct thorough user research to identify different audience groups and their specific needs, relationships to colonial history, and potential barriers to access.

Rationale: Understanding different user groups is essential for creating ethical and effective access strategies. As an expert emphasised:

So, who are your users? Identify first who are the people that are accessing your archives. Because it might be the case that it is important for researchers to have upfront information about the biases that you already have encountered? Or if you are going to engage with communities, they can be quite sensitive to certain terms—terms that were used in the past and that they might encounter today and that might make them sensitive to all these materials.⁶

This highlights how different users require different kinds of support and preparation when engaging with colonial archives.

Implementation:

⁵ Interview, Archives Decolonisation Project, 2024-25

⁶ Interview, Archives Decolonisation Project, 2024-25

- Identify key user groups (researchers, descendants, educators, community members)
- Conduct focused research with representatives from each group, particularly from formerly colonised regions
- Develop user personas that capture both practical needs and emotional relationships to colonial materials
- Map user journeys to identify barriers and support requirements at different stages
- Establish a feedback system for continuous improvement based on actual usage
- Include budget for compensating community participants in research activities
- Create an ethics framework for responsible user research

Priority Assessment:

- Tier: 2 (Moderate Priority - Partial Implementation)
- Resource Level: MODERATE-HIGH
- Implementation Complexity: MODERATE
- Impact: HIGH
- Rationale: Essential for user-centered design but requires sustained community engagement capacity. Start with basic user surveys and feedback mechanisms, expanding to comprehensive community research as engagement capabilities develop.

2.2 Digital Welcome Spaces

Recommendation: Develop differentiated digital entry points that acknowledge and honour each user group's unique relationship to colonial history while providing appropriate context and support.

Rationale: The VOC archives hold profoundly different meanings for different users. For academic researchers, they may represent historical evidence; for descendants of colonised peoples, they may contain painful family histories, evidence of ancestral trauma, or stories of resistance. Each group benefits from appropriate framing and support.

Implementation:

- Create distinct landing pages for different user categories (academic researchers, descendants, community groups, students) based on research from section 2.1
- Incorporate clear acknowledgments of colonial violence and archival limitations
- Create "journey guides" tailored to different research purposes (e.g., ancestral research, academic study, educational projects) with appropriate preparatory materials and support resources
- Feature testimonials and case studies showcasing diverse engagement approaches
- Offer different navigational paths tailored to expertise levels, research needs, and prior research
- Implement regular user testing with representatives from each group

Priority Assessment:

- Tier: 2 (Moderate Priority)

- Resource Level: MODERATE-HIGH
- Implementation Complexity: MODERATE-HIGH
- Impact: MODERATE-HIGH
- Rationale: Builds on user research findings; requires content creation for multiple audiences but provides differentiated access experiences. Can be developed incrementally starting with basic differentiated landing pages.

2.3 Emotional Accessibility

Recommendation: Create integrated digital tools that support users emotionally when encountering colonial violence in both historical content and terminology, while providing contextual understanding of imposed categories and derogatory language.

Rationale: Colonial archives contain material that provokes strong emotional responses, especially for descendants of colonised peoples. As one researcher emphasised: "When looking into sensitive history, it's important to have people around who have already had that experience."⁷

These reactions cross cultural and age boundaries, from researchers who "break down" to young students who experience physical distress. One researcher reported how offensive terminology used during archive introductions was "terrifying,"⁸ while another observed a child becoming physically ill when viewing images of enslaved people being transported.

These responses revealed a shared human reaction to historical violence that transcends background or personal connection. Both European and non-European participants reported similar distress, though they processed it differently. Digital platforms must develop mechanisms to address these emotional responses when users access materials without institutional support, potentially including contextual warnings, terminology guidance, and supportive resources.

Implementation:

- Design an emotional safety framework with three key components:
 - Preparation guides before engagement
 - Adjustable content filters during research
 - Post-engagement processing resources after difficult encounters
- Implement content warning systems that:
 - Provide advance notice of sensitive content before display
 - Use graduated warning systems based on content severity
 - Allow users to set personal thresholds and preferences
 - Integrate digital "emotional check-in" prompts throughout the user journey
- Develop contextual understanding through:
 - Clear explanations of historical terminology without normalising harmful language
 - Information about imposed categorisation systems
 - Multiple perspectives on categorisation systems

⁷ Interview, Archives Decolonisation Project, 2024-25

⁸ Interview, Archives Decolonisation Project, 2024-25

- Create virtual support spaces with:
 - Video testimonials from community members and researchers
 - Discussion spaces for shared processing
- Establish clear pathways to community support networks, professional help, and/or downloadable guides for offline processing and reflection
- Partner with community organisations to co-create appropriate support materials
- Evaluate and improve emotional support systems continuously

Priority Assessment:

- Tier: 2 (Moderate Priority)
- Resource Level: HIGH
- Implementation Complexity: HIGH
- Impact: HIGH
- Rationale: Critical for user safety but requires extensive development, testing, and ongoing support systems. Implement incrementally starting with basic content warnings and expanding to comprehensive emotional support tools.

2.4 Translation Support for Non-Dutch Speakers

Recommendation: Develop practical resources that help non-Dutch speakers navigate archival materials despite language barriers.

Rationale: Many potential users may not speak Dutch. As one expert noted: "You definitely need knowledge of Dutch... to navigate the archives."⁹ This approach acknowledges language barriers while offering practical tools to help users work with the archives using available resources.

Implementation:

- Create simple guides explaining translation challenges
- Provide how-to tutorials for using translation tools with historical documents
- Develop a dictionary of common administrative terms with clear explanations
- Add warning labels about biases in automated translations of colonial language
- Share resources for learning old Dutch and palaeography
- Set up forums where users can ask translation questions and get community help
- Connect with volunteer translation networks
- Build shared glossaries of difficult terms that everyone can reference

Priority Assessment:

- Tier: 1 (High Priority)
- Resource Level: LOW
- Implementation Complexity: LOW
- Impact: HIGH

⁹ Interview, Archives Decolonisation Project, 2024-25

- Rationale: Highly practical, addresses major accessibility barrier, can leverage existing tools and resources. Essential for global accessibility and can be implemented quickly with immediate user benefit.

2.5 Navigational Aids for Non-Expert Users

Recommendation: Develop intuitive digital navigation tools and critical technology education that empower users without archival expertise to effectively engage with colonial archives.

Rationale: Archives typically require specialised knowledge to navigate effectively. As one researcher noted: "You definitely need to understand the organisation of the archive. You need an idea about what one is looking for—from which region for instance. You need knowledge to navigate the archives."¹⁰

Beyond basic navigation, communities need to understand how digital systems themselves shape information access. As an expert explains, working with communities involves "training them...thinking about the potential they [digital systems] have to disrupt these communities in general. So they can take more decisions about what they want to do."¹¹

Implementation:

- Create visual guides showing how archives are organised
- Develop simple tutorials that teach basic navigation skills
- Provide ready-made research paths for beginners to follow
- Design intuitive search interfaces with visual relationship maps between documents
- Offer workshops on archive navigation and understanding digital tools
- Include transparent explanations of how search systems and data structures work
- Regularly collect user feedback to make ongoing improvements

Priority Assessment:

- Tier: 1 (High Priority)
- Resource Level: MODERATE
- Implementation Complexity: MODERATE
- Impact: HIGH
- Rationale: Essential for public launch success and democratising access. Builds on existing platform and technical capabilities.

3. Community Engagement Strategies

3.1 Community Knowledge Integration

Recommendation: Create digital spaces where communities can collectively interpret and add their perspectives, stories, and knowledge to colonial archives.

¹⁰ Interview, Archives Decolonisation Project, 2024-25

¹¹ Interview, Archives Decolonisation Project, 2024-25

Rationale: Colonial archives lack the perspectives of those who were colonised, and the knowledge communities hold through oral histories, memories, and traditions that may complement, contextualise, or challenge colonial archives. Integrating these perspectives creates a more complete historical understanding. As one curator explained:

I put it on the Miro boards for people to look at and then they could respond using the chat or post-its and write their comments....I downloaded the material in this way...because otherwise, if you don't do it like this, they [the communities] cannot all work with it.¹²

Implementation:

- Build simple annotation tools that let people add context to documents
- Create digital boards organised by theme where related documents can be discussed
- Enable community members to:
 - Add annotations, tags, and connections between documents (with multilingual support)
 - Share oral histories, memories, and traditional knowledge related to materials
 - Create special collections linking archival materials with community knowledge
 - Set privacy levels for annotations (public, community-only, or private)
- Connect community contributions directly to relevant archive documents
- Establish fair processes that respect both community knowledge and scholarly standards
- Create clear ownership policies for community-contributed knowledge

Priority Assessment:

- Tier: 3 (Lower Priority)
- Resource Level: VERY HIGH
- Implementation Complexity: VERY HIGH
- Impact: HIGH
- Rationale: Transformative but requires extensive moderation infrastructure and long-term community relationships. Consider partnership models rather than internal development due to sustainability and moderation concerns.

3.2 Digital Tools for Community Narratives

Recommendation: Provide tools for communities to create their own curated pathways through the archives and share creative responses from their perspectives.

Rationale: Different communities have specific narrative priorities and interests within colonial archives and need spaces to process and reinterpret archives through their own perspective, focusing on personal concerns rather than colonial facts. As a museum professional shared about her exhibition work: "For the communities, it was very important to have their narratives told in a certain way... when it was about colonialism, there always was

¹² Interview, Archives Decolonisation Project, 2024-25

the view that things like resistance should take the lead. And it should not be a story about victimhood."¹³

Implementation:

- Develop intuitive digital curation tools that let communities:
 - Create guided pathways through documents highlighting specific aspects of colonial history, such as resistance, resilience, agency, and lived experiences
 - Create and share artistic and creative responses to archival material
 - Organise virtual exhibits that tell their stories
- Implement sharing features so curated collections can be used by other organisations
- Provide technical support and training for digital curation skills
- Regularly feature community-created collections on the main platform
- Use clear licensing that protects community ownership of their stories
- Learn from successful community-led digitisation projects

Priority Assessment:

- Tier: 2 (Moderate Priority - Partial Implementation)
- Resource Level: HIGH
- Implementation Complexity: HIGH
- Impact: HIGH
- Rationale: High impact but requires significant technical development and ongoing moderation. Begin with read-only community curation tools (users create pathways through existing documents) before advancing to user-generated content, addressing sustainability concerns.

3.3 Supporting Community-Based Archival Needs

Recommendation: Develop programs and tools that support community-specific uses of archives, including personal heritage research, family disputes, and local governance needs.

Rationale: Archives serve critical practical functions for communities navigating post-colonial realities. As a researcher shared: "One of my informant[s]... asked me, 'Can you help me find archives about my ancestors?' Because he was engaged in [a] dispute... It's really sensitive for me, because it's a dispute, and also there's this stratification of people."¹⁴

Implementation:

- Design simple search tools for finding family and ancestral information
- Create step-by-step guides for exploring personal heritage
- Develop clear ethical guidelines for using archives in present-day disputes
- Partner with community advocates and legal advisors to provide guidance
- Create support networks connecting people researching similar topics

¹³ Interview, Archives Decolonisation Project, 2024-25

¹⁴ Interview, Archives Decolonisation Project, 2024-25

Priority Assessment:

- Tier: 3 (Lower Priority)
- Resource Level: HIGH
- Implementation Complexity: HIGH
- Impact: MODERATE-HIGH
- Rationale: Valuable community service but requires legal expertise and ongoing support infrastructure. Consider partnership with legal aid organisations rather than internal capacity building.

4. Decolonising Technical Systems

4.1 Decolonising Metadata Systems and Contextual Layers

Recommendation: Develop metadata systems that incorporate diverse worldviews, acknowledge historical violence, and provide contextual layers throughout the user experience.

Rationale: Standard metadata practices often reinforce colonial perspectives. As an expert pointed out, "In terms of the actual technical aspects... it is very important in terms of metadata to think about vocabularies and ontologies... [which] might not necessarily represent or include the violences, for instance, that go within those materials."¹⁵ Technology "makes you put on lenses through which you see the world,"¹⁶ making community participation essential to prevent dominant perspectives from being embedded in systems.

Implementation:

- Review existing metadata schemas for colonial biases while developing culturally appropriate terms with community input
- Create systems allowing for multiple, sometimes contradictory, descriptions of the same materials
- Design toggleable contextual panels that explain sensitive content and offer diverse perspectives
- Include community members in decision-making about metadata development and technical governance
- Document technical decisions and assess their impacts on different user groups
- Prioritise indigenous and community knowledge systems alongside academic classification methods

Priority Assessment:

- Tier: 3 (Lower Priority)
- Resource Level: VERY HIGH
- Implementation Complexity: VERY HIGH
- Impact: HIGH

¹⁵ Interview, Archives Decolonisation Project, 2024-25

¹⁶ Interview, Archives Decolonisation Project, 2024-25

- Rationale: Requires complete metadata overhaul and sustained community consultation. Foundational change best suited for major platform revision or long-term institutional development.

4.2 Accessible Technology and Interface Design

Recommendation: Build digital systems that work across different devices, internet conditions, and cultural contexts to ensure equitable access for all communities.

Rationale: High-tech solutions can exclude the very communities they intend to serve. One expert highlighted success with simple platforms: "They used WordPress... and it's this kind of thing that is just amazing because it acts as a repository." Additionally, interfaces should also consider cultural approaches to organising and navigating information, as "technology imposes a western lens in the majority of the world... that do not allow for other types of being in the world, other types of thinking about the world."¹⁷

Implementation:

- Evaluate and optimise accessibility across different contexts:
 - Areas with limited internet access
 - Different device types, operating systems, and browsers
 - Varying technical capabilities
- Develop mobile-first approaches where smartphones are the primary means of internet access
- Create offline options for areas with limited connectivity
- Use open-source and widely available platforms when possible
- Provide multiple pathways for accessing the same content based on user preferences and capabilities
- Where technically feasible, design interfaces that offer:
 - Story-based navigation for communities with narrative traditions
 - Simple alternatives to text-heavy interfaces
 - Multiple ways to interact with content beyond reading (audio, visual, interactive)
- Test all interfaces with representatives from target communities before implementation

Priority Assessment:

- Tier: 1 (High Priority)
- Resource Level: MODERATE
- Implementation Complexity: MODERATE
- Impact: HIGH
- Rationale: Critical for diverse global access; technical team can implement alongside existing development work. Essential for inclusive access and aligns with existing technical capabilities.

¹⁷ Interview, Archives Decolonisation Project, 2024-25

4.3 Enhanced Search Tools for Document Navigation and Discovery

Recommendation: Create precise search tools that help users find exactly what they need in complex archives.

Rationale: Current search functionality often lacks sufficient granularity, making it cumbersome to find specific materials. As a researcher explained:

Custom range in terms of years is something that is lacking in GLOBALISE...the global term is used, and at best you can separate them by volumes, but that is still not that handy, especially if I want to find it in custom years. Every volume has a year, alright, so indirectly I can figure it out. But directly it is a bit of a hassle.¹⁸

Implementation:

- Implement precise search filters for:
 - Exact date ranges
 - Specific geographical locations
 - Document types and sub-documents (e.g., distinguishing between reports and included letters)
- Solve archival challenges like:
 - Inconsistent folio and page numbering
 - Spelling variations of the same words
 - Searching within specific parts of documents (e.g., "find this term in letters with local princes, not in the main report")¹⁹
- Allow complex searches combining multiple criteria
- Allow users to save searches for ongoing research
- Test search tools with diverse users to ensure they work for everyone

Priority Assessment:

- Tier: 1 (High Priority)
- Resource Level: MODERATE
- Implementation Complexity: MODERATE-HIGH
- Impact: HIGH
- Rationale: Improves core functionality; technical solutions with clear specifications and measurable outcomes. Builds on existing platform capabilities and addresses immediate user needs.

5. Sustainable Decolonisation

5.1 Measuring Impact and Maintaining Transparency in Decolonisation Work

Recommendation: Develop evaluation frameworks that measure the impact of decolonisation efforts, centering community perspectives rather than traditional metrics. Maintain transparency about ongoing processes and learnings.

¹⁸ Interview, Archives Decolonisation Project, 2024-25

¹⁹ Interview, Archives Decolonisation Project, 2024-25

Rationale: Traditional metrics often fail to capture impacts of decolonisation efforts, which is an ongoing process rather than a destination. Success should include how communities engage with and benefit from archives. As one archive professional noted about their exhibition: "Young people here in the Netherlands who have a background from the Caribbean Island were amazed by all these histories... They felt strengthened by that history and they felt like their identity became a little better known to them."²⁰ Being transparent about both successes and challenges builds trust with communities and helps other institutions learn.

Implementation:

- Create a public-facing documentation platform about decolonisation efforts, sharing both success and challenges
- Co-create evaluation and success metrics with communities and stakeholders
- Collect stories and feedback showing how archives affect people's lives
- Create regular opportunities for community input and suggestions
- Create case studies demonstrating different approaches to decolonisation
- Build networks with others doing similar work to exchange knowledge
- Regularly review and adapt evaluation frameworks as community needs and priorities evolve over time

Priority Assessment:

- Tier: 3 (Lower Priority)
- Resource Level: MODERATE-HIGH
- Implementation Complexity: MODERATE
- Impact: MODERATE
- Rationale: Important for accountability but requires established community relationships and ongoing evaluation capacity. Better suited for implementation after foundational community engagement practices are established.

5.2 Multi-Archival Approaches to Address Colonial Silences

Recommendation: Build partnerships with diverse archives to include perspectives missing from colonial collections.

Rationale: Colonial archives primarily contain the coloniser's perspective. As one expert explained:

The National Heritage Institution only has certain materials, of course, from the colonial period, from the Dutch, so it's mostly the colonisers archive. So, it's very hard to find things that came from the Southeast Asian Community for example...we [therefore] included material from smaller towns in the Netherlands, because they were much more closer with these communities...We asked people from the communities that 'where can we find the material that you want us to include' and they pointed us to those archives.²¹

Implementation:

²⁰ Interview, Archives Decolonisation Project, 2024-25

²¹ Interview, Archives Decolonisation Project, 2024-25

- Map and develop partnerships with archives that offer different perspectives:
 - Collections identified by community members
 - Local archives with closer community connections
 - Private, family, and religious collections
- Establish processes for identifying, acknowledging, and addressing gaps in representation in colonial records
- Create formal and fair agreements for sharing materials across archives
- Establish protocols for acknowledging all contributing archives
- Include community advisors in identifying valuable archive partnerships
- Support smaller archives with technology and resources when needed
- Create sustainable relationships rather than one-time collaborations

Priority Assessment:

- Tier: 3 (Lower Priority)
- Resource Level: VERY HIGH
- Implementation Complexity: VERY HIGH
- Impact: MODERATE-HIGH
- Rationale: Excellent long-term goal but requires extensive partnerships and coordination beyond current project scope. Better suited for institutional partnership or dedicated funding initiatives.

5.3 Respecting Cultural and Religious Significance of Archival Material

Recommendation: Recognise that some archival materials are not just historical records but living cultural items, and create policies for access and potential repatriation requests.

Rationale: Many archival materials continue to serve vital roles in community identity and practices. As an expert explains through the example of traditional maps: "They are living documents because they do not only speak about the rights of land... but they [the community] might take these documents to petition for rain... there are rituals that we do to attract rain."

Communities maintain strong connections to these materials: "When you actually talk with the communities... they actually care very much about [these documents]. Even when they are not aware that they were somewhere else, in the moment that they realise that they are somewhere else, why would you not want to have documents of your great grandparent?"

Implementation:

- Create a transparent repatriation policy with clear request processes and criteria
- Develop digital alternatives when physical return is not possible
- Document cultural significance in metadata in collaboration with communities
- Train staff to handle cultural and religious questions respectfully
- Create regular reporting on repatriation requests and outcomes

Priority Assessment:

- Tier: 3 (Lower Priority)

- Resource Level: HIGH
- Implementation Complexity: HIGH
- Impact: MODERATE-HIGH
- Rationale: Critical ethical consideration but requires institutional policy framework better suited to National Archives or similar institutions with established repatriation procedures and legal frameworks.

5.4 Community Control of Living Cultural Heritage

Recommendation: Create governance systems that give communities meaningful authority over how their cultural materials are digitised, shared, and accessed in colonial archives.

Rationale: Digitising cultural materials extends colonial power dynamics into the digital realm, raising fundamental questions about ownership and control. As one expert explains:

We need to think very carefully about governance of data...If you have material that you are presenting in a collection that is outside the country... from a country that the material is originally from, I think we should be very mindful of what are the implications... the fact that it has sometimes been extracted violently... or not necessarily with violence, but simply extracting it is a form of violence. It's a form of getting a graph of the cultural knowledge and understanding of people and then uprooting it from the original place.²²

Digital archives must be prepared to engage meaningfully with new conversations about ownership and repatriation that digitisation will inevitably spark:

It's very important for us to think about what it means for communities that plant cultural and religious significance into these objects to be somewhere else... It might be a discussion that has not happened yet. But these digital objects can spark that kind of conversation.

Implementation:

- Create governance structures where source communities have final authority over:
 - Whether their cultural materials are digitised
 - How these materials are described and contextualised
 - Who can access them and under what conditions
- Create clear consent processes before digitising culturally sensitive materials
- Let communities set their own access rules for digital cultural materials
- Build systems where communities can update or remove digital content if needed
- Host regular discussions about ethical issues in digital cultural heritage
- Document evolving practices and share lessons learned

Priority Assessment:

- Tier: 3 (Lower Priority)
- Resource Level: VERY HIGH
- Implementation Complexity: VERY HIGH
- Impact: HIGH

²² Interview, Archives Decolonisation Project, 2024-25

- Rationale: Transformative recommendation requiring dedicated institutional commitment and specialised expertise in indigenous data sovereignty. This fundamental governance restructuring deserves proper resources and partnership with organisations equipped to support authentic community control over cultural heritage.

Conclusion

The GLOBALISE research infrastructure can become more than a repository of colonial documents. It demonstrates the potential to become a living digital space where communities face difficult histories, tell new stories, and begin to heal together. Decolonisation is not a feature to be added but requires reorienting how we understand archives—centering care, agency, and community knowledge to build more just relationships with both the past and present.

Colonial records continue to shape contemporary realities, making this work urgent and consequential. The task of decolonising archives extends beyond making historical materials accessible; it involves creating tools that empower communities to understand, challenge, and transform persistent colonial structures in our societies.

This work won't be easy. It requires sustained commitment, ongoing reflection, and genuine partnerships. Yet the potential rewards—more complete historical understanding, repaired relationships, and strengthened community agency—make this difficult journey worth taking. The prioritisation framework integrated throughout this report acknowledges these challenges while providing a realistic roadmap that balances immediate accessibility needs with long-term transformative goals.

By engaging with these recommendations in a strategic, phased manner, GLOBALISE and similar projects can help build a more honest and fair relationship with our shared history that has been experienced so differently by different groups.

TRANSCRIPTS

INTERVIEW 1 | Professor and Co-Director of Digital Humanities Centre at a major UK university | Application of digital technologies to colonial historical research.

A: Hi. Hello. How are you doing? How are you?

P: I'm good. How are you? It's very nice to meet you.

A: Yeah, likewise. Thank you so much for being ever so generous with your time. I truly appreciate it.

P: No problem. So, before we begin, how do you pronounce your name?

A: It's A.

P: A. Right. I was sure I was butchering your name.

A: It's all right. It's honestly a pretty difficult name anywhere I go, including South Asia. So I'm pretty used to like it being bastardized at this point. So I don't mind one bit. And what do you prefer going by? I see you've written P on the screen.

P: I prefer P. If you call me P, I will feel like, you know, when I was ten years old and my mother would shout at me "P, P". Better P. So tell me A. So, A told me about the work you're doing, but I'd love to hear more about what you have to say about it and anything that I can do to help.

A: Sure. I don't know how aware you are of the GLOBALISE project, but um I take it you're a little bit aware of the same. So, I'm by training an anthropologist and I'm currently a guest researcher on the GLOBALISE project. And what I'm really thinking about is how communities, particularly from erstwhile colonized countries relate to these archives, how they experience accessing it and also like how we can improve that process, both of like enabling that access, but also just once they do have access, how to make it safe and meaningful for them to access this material because there is a lot of problematic stuff in there. And I'm particularly, of course, thinking of more non-technical accessibility—So going beyond the technical aspects. And I know you're quite the expert on those matters, but so it'll be nice to hear a bit of both like what you've done both with respect to like technical accessibility, but also beyond that. So that's a very simply it. And yeah, I'm primarily interviewing people from both experts, non-experts, and yeah, will think with that material eventually.

P: Perfect. Um let me think about these. I mean, many things come to my mind, while you were just, you know, talking about what you are doing. I mean, I it's quite safe to start from the point of departure in which we know that every single archive is biased—whether you like it or not, whether it is colonial or not, but particularly colonial archives tend to suffer more acutely, I will say, of particular types of biases, right? So, whether these are gender, racial,

age related, obviously, social class also, um, you know, there are quite a lot of biases in terms also of what are the voices that can be recorded in colonial archives, right?

It's quite important to acknowledge that. One of the things that I will say, in terms of working with colonial archives, particularly you are making these available in some sort of way, I would say there are different aspects to accessing information in archives that you can think about. So, what is the kind of like, not only the life cycle of the data, let's say, but also the ways in which your users engage with this information. So, what I'm talking about is— So, who are your users? So, identifying first who are the people that are accessing your archives. Because it might be the case that it is important for researchers to have upfront information about the biases that you already have encountered? Or if you are going to engage with communities, they can be quite sensitive to certain terms—terms that were used in the past and that they might encounter today and that might make them, sensible to all these materials. I think you might want to have, for instance, information upfront in your collection—to begin with, what are the kinds of biases that you will encounter in this collection, in these archive. And tailor it to the users that you are engaging with. So, I will say the first thing for me—in thinking about archives, and something that to me is very important—is to be up front: what is the material that we have, what is the nature of the collection, because, in our case, for instance, we work with like Latin American Archives. I work particularly with the National Heritage Institution in Latin America. And there are many people that might say, well, you know, you have quite a lot of indigenous data in there, which is certainly true, but not ALL indigenous data. So, this is to say that you might have discourses of particular social classes at different times—so it's not the same like looking at the collections of the 16th century, from the 19th century. And so, it requires not only awareness of the material, but also more historical knowledge of what is happening with that material, right? So that would be, you know, one of the first things for me to say, right? Like, make sure that you know who your audience in the project is and who are your building this material for, and then to be very very upfront about what are the biases that you are encountering and that you are seeing. And maybe you might also want to take that opportunity for communities to be participatory with you, right? To say, are you encountering things here that you think do not represent you today, that you think we should make other people aware about. I think that's very good. That's a very good starting point. So, that will be mainly about the non-technical kind of aspects, right?

In terms of the actual technical aspects of, you know, thinking about data and information and how these things engage. So, I will say it is very important in terms of metadata to think about vocabularies and ontologies. So, how archivists, how librarians, how information technology people describe collections might not necessarily represent or include the violences, for instance, that go within those materials, right?

So I think to start making aware, your team as well, that there might be collections that...so I'm just going to give you an example of this. So, um, we work, for instance, with collections for the inquisition.. And so the inquisition in Region in Latin America] is absolutely brutal, especially when they deal, for instance, with what they think of as witches, wizards and, you know, this kind of approach that they have to indigenous medics, which are basically, you know, medical doctors, but conceived in this way that make them basically, uh, in communion with demons and all sorts of different things. And so, the ways in which they get

described, right, into these records is quite derogative, it is quite specific, you know, there are vocabularies that go with that.

And so, whether you want to start thinking about ontologies of violence there and actually inform that to within, you know, the actual ontologies that you use in link open data for instance, right, on these technologies, um, is something that you could think about as well, right?

Um, the was very good material that was just released—I was actually in a workshop yesterday, that I want to show you. There is a project here in the UK called “Towards a National collection,” which is a fantastic project—it is a nationwide endeavour, where they are basically thinking about how the whole of the UK should mount collections together and the infrastructure behind it. And they commission a fantastic piece of research and teaching materials that are now called “Towards Digital Collections.” and I'm just going to put this in the chat, so you can have a look at it. So this is on Canvas that you can have a look at it straight away—this kind of like teaching resource. Okay, great. Yes, so um this is landing page so you will basically arrive there. Um, and you can see, you know, the production of it and whatever, right. But if you go to the part of Modules, you will have a bunch to bring interesting resources looking into collections in general, how collections are managed from actual basic level to advanced level. And there is good section about biases in collections. I think you will find interesting. Yeah, and I mean there are all sorts of different types of materials in there that can be useful for you, but it's supposed to be really a kind of like starting point on how GLAMS—so galleries, libraries, archives and museums—are thinking about the presentation of biases in collections, right? So that's an approach that you can they can follow.

One of the things that I will say is that there is no one right way of doing this. Because we have so many differences in the violences that people are subject to, during colonial periods and sometimes even today, right—we are not still out of colonialism as you know. We are still experiencing all sorts of different problems in terms of presentation of collections, but also in terms of actually, you know, communities engaging with these materials. And so, we need to think very carefully as well about, governance of data. So, this is to say that if you have material that you are presenting in a collection that is outside the country, right? From a country that the material is originally from, um I think we should be very mindful of what the implications of these material bringing up ? and the fact that it has sometimes been extracted violently and you know, or not necessarily with violence, but simply extracting it is a form of violence, right? It's a form of getting a graph of the cultural knowledge and understanding of people and then and then um uprooting it from, you know, the original place. And I think um it's very important for us to think about what it means for communities that plants cultural and religious significance into these objects to be somewhere else, right? And it might be a discussion that is not in the community, yet right? That has not happened yet. But these digital objects, for instance, can spark that kind of conversation and, I think that is really very interesting and very important to be aware about.

So just an example, in Region in Latin America, we have these documents, that are maps—so in Region in Latin America, in the whole of America, before the arrival of the Spanish, the tradition of writing was by painting. So, we had all sorts of books, right, maps and things like that, but were basically paintings, little graphics. There are all sorts of types of

activities that happened with these objects, with these paintings, right? And while the West think of them as cartographic outputs, as maps, many of our indigenous communities actually take them as living documents. And they are living documents because they do not only speak about the rights of land, for instance, but they might, you know, take these documents to the petitions of rain, for instance, right? So, we have in Region in Latin America, for instance, there are rituals that we do, uh, to attract rain. So you go to the top of the mountain and you say different prayers. and today that kind of ritual takes a very interesting form of mixture between Catholicism and all sorts of indigenous beliefs, so it's a mixture now of Christianity with indigenous beliefs basically, But they perform a ritual to a saint in this case, to ask for ring, but you will take the document to the mountain as a testimony of who you are. So many of these documents, for instance, in the case of Region in Latin America have been extracted right? And now live in the British Museum—they are therefore preserved as a particular historical event but in reality, the communities, for instance, might have a photocopy of these documents, right? And they still perform rituals like these and so on, right?

So, what is our responsibility, right? What is the responsibility of an archive or of a museum, of cultural institutions in general, of either bringing these objects back—so repatriation of objects is a quite an important conversation there. Or what are the consequences for people in general, you know, of having these objects somewhere else. I have seen many people argue that, “oh well, you know, they were taken out centuries ago and there is a disconnection.” And when you actually talk with the communities no, they actually care very much about them. So, you know, even when they are not aware that they were somewhere else, in the moment that they realize that they are somewhere else, why would you not want to have documents of your great grandparent? Yeah, I know, like there are all sorts of interactions with communities that are happening in that sense. Um yeah, so I don't know if this is the kind of thing.

A: Yeah, this is perfect, but I also wanted to ask you....like, this is something I just overheard, so I may be wrong, but L, I don't know if you've met him, but he's also on the GLOBALISE project. He was saying that your archival project did some sort of a road show as well. Is that true? A sort of a road show to take the archive in a way to the community. I maybe wrong about this but...

P: No, we haven't, but that would be incredible. I was just going to say that what we do is that we work directly with the communities, right? So, we have, for instance, just to give you an idea of some of the things that we do—in reality, it is a funny thing....because I work in this intersection with archives—but in reality what we are doing is creating computational approaches to identifying information from historical material. This is really kind of.... because we have cases histories which have to do with history, right? But because of the nature of our collections, we needed basically to engage with all these different issues and all these different concerns.

So, one of the things that we have been doing has been precisely to work with indigenous scholars directly, and indigenous people as well directly in documents, for instance, that we might interested on. So just to give you an example, for instance, we are working at the moment on the creation of computer vision models for text recognition, with transcribed material (?) right? We are doing models for 16 and 17th century Spanish, but we are also

doing a model for now what was the language of the Aztec, right? And so, there are still many communities in Region in Latin America that speak now, and so we work with our community in Region in Latin America, with indigenous scholars in these actual collections, right? So, um, yeah, that's kind of like one of the main interactions that we have.

A: If you can further elaborate on what the nature of engagement looks like, that would be really lovely?

P: We have been working with this community for quite a while, right? So, there are basically three communities within. I call them one community but in reality, there are three. They are in the Indigenous region, and in Region in Latin America further to the coast. So some of the things that we started doing many years ago was the archaeological atlas of the area, right? So, we wanted basically to report all their archaeological places that are in that region. And they happen to be living in one of the main archaeological areas of that region. Their ancestors are from there and they are probably direct descendants of the people that are from that archaeological site. And I did that work when I was back in Region in Latin America working with the National Research Institute. So, that was kind of like a top down approach, like an institutional endeavour—where you go and you record an archaeological site. In Region in Latin America, we have very strict laws regarding archaeological sites. So, everything is recorded, who he's where and everything else, right? And so, they have obviously the right of land and everything, but it is recorded in the national atlas of archaeology, that it is a specific site right. But that was kind of like our first interaction with them, right?

And then later on, another archaeologist, a friend of mine, started working on the conceptions of the space and place with them. They tend to have quite different kind of Spanish Christian concepts of space and place. And so, we started recording oral histories about, you know, the places that they are living, the landscapes in general, and we started recording as well, stories about the nature of their houses. So, what they call home, and how that has changed over time, how that differs, right? So, that was kind of like our first point of contact and interactions with them.

And then, as we have been, you know, progressing over time with projects and things like that, we have been working with them in specific projects, thinking about technology and what technology does to their communities, how the communities change because of technology,—things like the mobile phone, things like WhatsApp, things like all of these all these kind of technologies, banking apps, for instance. So it's a kind of like in between anthropological approach and archaeological-historical approach as well.

And then we have worked with the younger generations in the community on these more computational projects, right? So, we have been doing training with them and how to understand what computers do? And thinking about what artificial intelligence is? And like all these different things that come to their place and then the potential they have to disrupt these communities in general. So they can take more decisions of what they want to do. So that has been kind of like our ways of working with them, yes.

A: Yeah, interesting. And I read in one or two of your papers, about low digital literacy rates. And the other thing you spoke about is something that I'm not aware of at all, which is the

tangible user interface. So, that was one and if you can elaborate on that and how you were thinking about it. And then the second, I also saw you did a project—an exhibition—called the Exhibition project. And there was this interesting line in that which said “physical tools when engaging with digital content.” So if you can also elaborate on that and just generally your experience of that exhibition and what that opened up, perhaps, or yeah?

P: I think it would be fantastic if you speak with my husband because he was the one that directed all the exhibition project part. He led that project, and he happens to be in the director of the collection (?), so I'll send you know his details. You can make an appointment with him. He has worked for quite a long time on the colonial theory, but also on how to approach collections in general. and he did his PhD on human computer interaction.

So, one of the things that we have been thinking about in the past few years is, how we think.... that technology is fantastic, right? We are digital humanists, and we tend to think that technology brings a lot of very good things, in terms of research and life in general, right? But one of the things that, that is not obvious, but straight away when you start is one of those things that once you see, you cannot unsee. One of one of the things that you realize the straightaway about technology is that um it makes you put on lenses, right, or a type of lens through which you see the world. And that means that many of the things, many of the ways in which, people in the global south might think about the world is not represented in the technology that we use.

So, an example of this, right? You have used Google maps, right? This is a type of geographic information system, right? And when you ask a classroom to think about space and place, right? And you ask them “draw me a map,” right? “Draw me a map from your house to university, right? And this is an exercise that I do with my students in the Master's level and very much fun to see, right? And to get them to think of a map, of people coming here and there and what you get is what you will see in google maps, right? But what you are inadvertently, very much doing, is portraying space and place, in very much a western way. So, this is a Cartesian, Euclidian, tall (?) man's conception of the world, of space and place. And when you look at how people, for instance, in the Indigenous region that I was telling you about earlier, conceive of space and place—this bird's eye view of the world is not the way in which they conceive space and place.

So, what I'm saying here is that technology imposes a western lens in the majority of the world, because at the end of the day, both technology and particularly now things like artificial intelligence is basically created and developed by men, visually white, middle age, living in the global north. So, you will have these lenses right, that do not allow for other types of being in the world, other types of thinking about the world. And so, in terms of what we talk about human computer interaction is precisely to think about how we can decolonise technology, right? Because mathematics there are mathematics here, right? So numbers in a way are certainly the universal language. And so, despite that computers are the same in that they work with one on zeros, right? So, how can we create technologies that trade (?) different ideas about the world, right? So, it's the same with the conception of time, right? So, we conceive of time as linear, right? So, we conceive of a past, present, and future, but there are societies that will conceive of time as circular, as spiral, right? So, how can we do this kind of portrayals into technology, and one of the ways of thinking about it is through human computer interaction. So, the interfaces that you normally get are graphical user interfaces.

This is what you get in computers. But, what about for instance, working with objects instead of [having] to interact with the computer or the graphical user interfaces that we have. So, this along those lines, so these ideas are basically on along those lines.

Regarding the exhibition project, that was a fantastic project — it was very much fun. My husband basically built this kind of tower which was an interactive display basically, where you put yourself in front of it and you can touch one of the faces, for instance, of the object and then you will hear the music of that particular community and the idea was basically to think about how can you use historical music that has an archive, but that had to do at some point, with the transatlantic slave trade, right? So, to think about how African music has influenced the world, at a completely global scale. And that you recognize that in the music of people's ritual (?), for instance, but it is there right. And so yeah, so the interactive display was basically about that.

And we had students and we had a staff, we have members of the public basically, who have come to that. I can send you as well, J can tell you more about the project and how that happened. So, I will send you J's details anyway, so..

A: And so as a medium, how is an exhibition in some ways, useful or not useful for like opening up something like the archives to the general public.

P: I think that was really interesting. We didn't have at that point the time for a proper follow up, which would have been, you know, kind of like performing some sorts of interviews and, thinking more about what the public is thinking about, you know, the exhibition and everything. But, at the end of the day, very much our intention was to make people, particularly students and staff, aware of not only, (the extent?) of the slave trade, but also the fact that...working for a 20 years in the UK, one of the things that I find all the time is that, people seem to have this perception that Europe exported knowledge. And that Europe has been, in a way or another, the point of creation of all sorts of differing types of knowledge. And in reality, what research is saying is that yeah, sure, they create some sorts of knowledge, but in the majority of the cases, particularly in the early modern period, after the Conquest of America and so on, it is very much the case that, before that, even before the early modern period, but before that, but particularly in the early modern period, which is, you know, the opening of the modern world in a way, what Europe or what we call Europeans now, right? but at least in the case of Region in Latin America, for instance, in Latin America in general, what the Spanish people are basically doing is taking the knowledge from somewhere else, repackaging it in some sort of way, claiming it as a discovery and then, you know, claiming that this is the European knowledge. And this is not the case at all, right? So, we have this with like medical knowledge substantially. In Region in Latin America, for instance, we have these amazing knowledge about plants, the same as in South Asian country, right...So you have astonishing amounts of information and knowledge about what plants do, and in the early modern i period, one of the things that happened is that, the Spanish king—Philip the second— in the middle of the 16th century, sends the royal medics to the whole of what they call the “Royalty of New Spain”—So the whole of Region in Latin America, Costo Rica and Guatemala and so on, to record medical knowledge about plants. And uh they create these amazing picture numbers of medicine scenes, right? They create these amazing pictures of medicines. They rename the plants...they record the indigenous names but they rename the plants into Latin names, and

then they say that indigenous people know nothing about these things. They create these new plant dictionaries in Europe, and then the medical revolutions of the 18th and 19th century happen and they say, well, you know, this is our fantastic knowledge. It is not. It is indigenous knowledge, basically, right?

So, yeah...so the idea behind the exhibition project, was precisely to create that kind of awareness through the music right? To say, music today, in the early modern period, has been profoundly influenced by the African the Diaspora. So, this is a way of showing that, you know, from the 15th century that you have some sorts of recordings and through, you know, paper writing from the Beatles to, you know, to pop music today and so on like that. You know, African music is influencing, like all over the world, right?

A: And I'm still defining this term for myself, but I guess what do you understand by decolonization, specifically in the context of your archival project? And then, you know, you're also speaking about these many viewpoints and of like Europe exporting knowledge to the rest of the world. So like, how do you contend with some of these many epistemes within your work and institution as well, like, you know, it could be just like hiring a diverse team, but like if there are other like practices that, you have incorporated in your work, that would be lovely to hear also about?

P: I think that's so important. It's quite interesting to see about the decolonisation, is many times labelled as a theory, it is not a theory. It is something that we need to live right? It a practice. I mean, I'm in between worlds.....because in a way growing up as a white person in Region in Latin America, in an educated family, gives me a perspective of the world that is very privileged, right? And at the same time half of my family comes from an indigenous tradition, right? And it is always in-between absorbing this national rhetoric where everything European is better, if you are white, you are better, if you know, if you are white, you are richer, if you are white... all these kinds of discourses are very much getting ingrained, I think, in, you know, who we are as a nation and how we think about the world. And encountering the fact that all these are basically lies, because when you start seeing the history of the conquest [inaudible]...you straightway start realizing that to begin with the conquest of America was not done by the Spanish, it was done by the classical (?).

A: Sorry, I don't know.

P: Yeah, so in there is this idea that the Spanish come to Region in Latin America, right? And that then they perform from Region in Latin America, the conquest of the rest of America. They obviously arrive first to the Caribbean with Christopher Columbus and so on and they do that there. And then when remember Arlando Cortes ? gets to Region in Latin America, there is the fall of what they call the Aztec empire—it is not actually in power anyway—but yeah, but it has been called like that. This is a colonizing concept you know. And then history goes that from that, you know, the Spanish colonized the rest of America. This is not true at all. What they encounter basically is very, very strong independent organizations which have been called 'Kingdoms', but they are not kingdoms in the reality. They are what we call antiquity (?). So these are forms of organizations that have a military branch, that have economic organization, and (?) was one of the most advanced cities in the world of the time. You have 200,000 people in a place, you know, living... when North Paris or north London has that number. They have running water in every single house, there was free education, I

can go on right and all these things you don't get to know, right? Like the story is like, "oh, no, yeah, the Spanish with their magic horses, and their amazing weapons, they come conquest everything, because indigenous people are idiots and, they believe they are gods, right?" This is all not true, right? (*Emphatic*). When you see all historical evidence you see the fact that these are all legends that are built to towards the end of the 17 and 18th centuries to discredit very much all indigenous organization that is at heart. And the neighbours of the Aztecs, which are called Tsaltecas (?), which are the same ethnic group, but they are different organization. They are the enemies of the Aztecs. So, when the Spanish arrive, they band with the Spanish because they think great, great opportunity to get rid of the Aztecs. So, they band with them, and they defeat the Aztec, and it is there are 2,000 soldiers who take all of Region in Latin America, not the 600 that Cortes had at the time. So after that, all the conquest of America upto Peru is performed by classical Tsaltecas soldiers. And they have massive power upto the end of the 17th century. And the Spanish realize that at the time that there is no way that they are going to control those territories with the Tsaltecas there. So, they start to do all sorts of different, very interesting political and social manoeuvres to get rid of them. And they do. By the 18th century they actually do. So, there are all these different narratives, that means that we have been lied to completely about who we are, how we come to be, our nationalism isn't true, you know, all these different aspects, right?

And I think for me, decolonization is the practice of critically thinking about what Europe has told us, right? In general, whoever colonial power came to your region, whatever that is, told you, because there have been active lies? So, for me, it is this process of not only analysing the layers of complexity and getting rid of the lies that we have been told all this time. Analysis of historical knowledge and so on. But also empower basically those who have been silenced by the dynamics of the colonial power, right? And I don't mean in a patronizing way. I mean in a collaborative, equally horizontal, way of thinking. So, yeah, so this is what it is for me.

If you haven't read the book, I would recommend you read, it is just out of this world, it is really good. It's called the Dawn of Everything.

A: Oh, yeah, yeah, I have read it. Yeah, it's fantastic. In fact, I was thinking of that when you were talking about, you know, of the lies we've been told, but....and in fact, it talks so much about the America because, you know, that is also David Gabe's specialization.

So, very quickly, just to return to the previous point, which is to say like how in practice, in your team, say for instance, or on your project, you may be contending with some of these Western epistemologies or, you know, power structure so to say.

P: I completely missed the first part of what you were saying...the internet was going....

A: No worries. Just to come back to the previous point, which was to say on your team or on your project, what are the practices, that you are undertaking to like, quote unquote, decolonize.

P: So, one of the things that I think about in team building is that it's not only necessary to have people that are experts on you know, particular topics, the topics that you are thinking

with. But also to have people in all stages of career and people that do not necessarily belong to Academia, right? So, I think that's a very important part that, I have learned over time. And in our team now, on the latest project that I'm working on, which is the (?) of New Spain, we have a very diverse team. Diverse not only in the sense of ... so we have from fantastic super experts in the topics of maritime biology or in digital humanities. But we also have people who are students, who are PhDs, post docs, professors, you know, we have all sorts of different career levels. And then we have people from all the different countries that will work with. And also, indigenous communities. So, we have people working with those in different parts—some of them don't even have university, right? But they are part of the project, as part of this research project as such. So, you know, I think that's very important to have to open these of projects as well to people that are not necessarily in academia and who never pursued an academic career, right?

A: Super and last, is your archival infrastructure public now? Who are the users you anticipate you know, because initially you said, you know, you have to think of the users. And of course we can think to a certain extent, but if it is going to be out there in the world, I don't know how to anticipate every kind of user.

P: So, you will not be able to, but certainly.... We were talking about precisely this in our workshop yesterday. I think that is true. I mean, you cannot anticipate everyone. But it is also true that there is a danger to not thinking of who your users will be. Because it is true that you can start from at least a point where, you knowing that you are going to be engaging with researchers, particularly, and there are particular conditions in your dataset, in your archive and, you know, whatever you are going to create, that you need to consider, that you need to think about—not only socially but also technologically. There is a concept that my husband, J, promotes quite a lot and that always makes me think about this, is that we need to think about this problem as socio-technical machines, right? So, it's not only the technology that you need to think about. So we might need to think, okay, I might use linked open data or whatever you want, and you might have the most advanced engines, but if you haven't thought about who is going to do that thing, right? Or why people might be interested in this or that, then, you know, you might run into problems right. Yeah, it's more meaningful to think about who you are working with.

So, in our particular case, at the moment we are building both our archives...so, across many different projects, I have this data, right? So, we have a (?) repositories where we data, and we keep the data in different ways, in different formats, for different people. So, to begin with, we have deposited all our data, for instance, with the National Data Repository.

So, for instance, for the beginning to early colonial Latin America project, we created these 16th century digital gazetteer of Spain, which contains around 15,000 place names recorded and everything, right? And so that data set, we deposited in the UK data service, but we also make it available to our website and for our data repository for anyone else.

Now in the new project that we are working on, where we are creating now, a proper archive of material and so on. We haven't made it public because it's going to be first our research infrastructure. And so, for that, I know, that my users are going to be academics, right? I know that for sure. So, what I'm thinking about is how to build, a platform, a repository, with all the actual things that a researcher would look for, would need.

And if I was thinking in terms of engagement with communities, what I would basically do is to go into these communities and ask them what do you want and what would you like. You know, what are things that will be useful for you to have, right?

A: I think we are reaching the end of our time.

P: J's email

A: Sure. Can I ask you one last question before you go, which is, if you have seen other archives or any kind of institutions really, who are doing interesting work according to you, that I could also further look at and explore in terms of particularly I guess engaging with uh communities.

P: Uh. I'll send you an email. Sure. because I can't recall at the moment the specific names. Region in Latin America, for instance, have very interesting initiatives, and we can put you in contact with as well.... But um these are initiatives on repositories, for instance, on how to work with communities particularly, so they have adopted, for instance, kind of like lower end technologies, um. So, for instance, there is a project called Daniaka (?) and they used word press. Okay. And is this kind of thing that is just amazing because it acts as a repository, it has adopted in Latin America as well, as a platform to create archives in WordPress. So, this approach, right, of thinking, okay, communities might not have the chance of going through link open data to going to, you know, or a particular or specific software, because you don't have the money for that, but there are other approaches, right, that we might take. And I think, for instance, has been quite interesting in their approach.

I will send you one from South Asia and another one for from Middle Eastern country, another from Africa.

A: Thank you so much. Thank you so very much. It was really a pleasure.

P: I hope that that was useful, but you know, contact with me whenever you want. I will be happy to, you know, have more conversations.

A: Thank you so much. I might actually hit you up again.

P: No problem. Okay. All right, have a good day. meet you. Likewise, bye.

INTERVIEW 2 | Lecturer in Heritage Theory, UNESCO Chair holder | Museum collections, colonial legacies, and Islamic cultural representation

M: Hi, my name is M

A: My name is A

M: Hello. Nice to meet you.

A: Yeah, likewise. Thank you so much for joining. I truly appreciate it...So shall I give you a quick introduction about myself and then perhaps, you can give me one too. So, I'm an anthropologist by training and currently I'm working on something called the GLOBALISE project, which is essentially digitising five million pages of the VOC archives, much more Asia related. And so, my role there is to really think about how to make this archival infrastructure more accessible to, particularly users from the global south. And just more inclusive, you know...it has a lot of derogatory language and a lot of silences and so to really think about, practices whereby we can overcome these shortcomings and such that, you know, it's actually an archive people are not traumatized by, but also its productive for people from the global south...because right now I've been hearing like for instance, from the national heritage institution, how like oftentimes people break down in the reading room. So, really to understand what that experience looks like and then how we can do better with regards to the GLOBALISE infrastructure. So that's largely about me and it'll be really nice to hear about you and if you have thoughts on the matter.

M: Yeah, I have not worked much on the VOC archives. I work more with or on the 19th century and 20th century colonial archives. You also came through to us through the exhibition we curated, and this exhibition had some VOC material, but mostly also from the 19th and uh 20th century. Okay. But, um yeah, the problems are similar, I would say. Yeah, what would you like to know?

A: It would be nice to hear us a little bit about this exhibition you organized and, how the reception was and, yeah, just about it for instance and whether that, you know, um I don't know the community archives very well, but if there are a silences there or, you know, uh things have been misconstrued or famed a certain way, then how do you undo that today in the contemporary moment? Do you or do you not? How various people engage with that exhibition and particularly of course Muslims themselves.

M: Yeah, so we curated the exhibition largely with the national heritage institution material, that was also limitation that they set...or that they didn't set it but it turned out to be a condition along the way. And that's really hard because the national heritage institution only has certain materials, of course, from the colonial period, from the Dutch, so it's mostly the colonizers archive. So, it's very hard to find things that came from the Southeast Asian Community, for example.

Um but the exhibition was about the Netherlands and the first Muslim communities here...from the 1920s onwards. First, there were Southeast Asian Community, and then also uh South Asia, um from Caribbean Community—with both roots in South Asia and Southeast Asia. So, it was about that, and it's a very little-known story in the Netherlands.

Because every time we think of Muslims, the focus is always on the Mediterranean communities. So the exhibition was about unsilencing that story and to bring colonialism into the narrative or the Dutch relationship to Islam.

We worked with materials from the national heritage institution, but we made the exhibition in co-creation with the communities that were involved in the exhibition and also with um, you know, our group of volunteers from the Community archives and most of them are Mediterranean because those are the largest communities here. So we also had Dutch people with roots in Mediterranean Communities look at the VOC and the colonial material related to Southeast Asia or South Asia. And give them their opinion and also, we made a selection.

So, what we did is, we made a broad selection and then made a more narrow selection based on the responses of different people. So yeah, that's how we worked. So, um yeah, so since we had both the communities looking at the materials and the broader Muslim community who are not necessarily related to these materials—Um, so there are different ideas.

For the communities, it was very important to have their narratives told in a certain way and have certain aspects of their story to be represented. So um that of course, I was actous (?) and so we made the (*narrower* ?) selection according to what they thought was important. For example, when it was about colonialism, there always uh that things like resistance should take the lead. And it should not be a story about victimhood (!) and how to tell the story about resistance, also through Islam. So, um, yeah, that's how we made this selection, with these things in mind.

A: Were there any other topics that these communities' thought were relevant other than resistance that they wanted featured, so to say, in the exhibition—just like more examples are wonderful to hear about.

M: The communities like the Southeast Asian Community, they have specific topics that they want to be included, which are inherent to their community. For example, the Southeast Asian community wanted to have a narrative about nationalism and the struggle for independence, also the struggle in independence that was done by Southeast Asian Muslims living in the Netherlands. Because that was our topic of course. It was about Muslims living in Netherlands and then you can tell different stories, but what they wanted to emphasize was the nationalism that was already there and how the Southeast Asian Community united with different faiths, and with different ethnic backgrounds, how they united to end this struggle. So there were certain documents testifying to that, and when we were making a selection, for example, these were the documents they chose. Which is not necessarily a story that is interesting to other Muslims in the NL or to the non-Muslim Dutch people, but this is what they wanted to emphasize, so this is what we selected.

And for example, and the specific Southeast Asian Muslim community, they have a very specific story that they wanted to tell, which involves their movement through different cities in the NL. So, they wanted all these cities to be represented for example. And they wanted the story of how they were betrayed by the Dutch in the late colonial period or straight after independence. Of course, this is a very well-known story, and they wanted this to be part of the exhibition.

And for the other people (other Muslim communities), they wanted to see more about how Islam was practiced in these regions during colonialism or before colonialism, so that was also part of the exhibition. This is how we used the VOC materials for example, to show um the sultanates that were present there before colonialism.

A: Interesting. So if you really got a bunch of different perspectives and that's really interesting. And did you also get the non-Muslim Dutch perspective and what they were more interested in?

M: Ah no we did not get those perspectives because we didn't make the exhibition for them. Just that they are the regular audience of the National Heritage Institution exhibition space. So, they were there, but they thought I don't know...I think what I heard from my colleagues was that for them what was most surprising was that they never realized that there were Muslims in the Netherlands before the Mediterranean Communities were here. And they arrived in the late 60s. So this is a story that's much earlier.

A: And other than in an exhibition format, have there been any other formats that you have presented some of this material or um yeah, like workshops, or any other kind of format, so to say.

M: Um not this material, no. My work is on the colonial archives as well, so um I have presented that, but that's very different topic. And also again, I don't work on the VOC period, only on the late colonial period period.

A: Got it. And how did the partnership with the National Heritage Institution come about and yeah, what was the nature of that and

M: They invited us to make an exhibition and umm yeah, they had a gap in their programming and then they thought, okay, let's fill the gap, and ask communities to make an exhibition with us or for us...hahahahaha...it was not really that clear. And uh yeah, that's what we did.

But the biggest struggle for us was that the archive is not representative of the Muslim communities in the Netherlands. So, we could work with the colonial archives—there's a lot, of course—but not that well. Like I said, it's just that because I work a lot with the colonial material and I know the archive, I know what I can find. But other than that it would have been very difficult to find Muslim perspectives in the archives because it's a Dutch government archives. So, there's a lot about Islam, there's a lot about Muslims, but always from the perspective of the colonial administration. That's not necessarily a story that we wanted to tell. And there is very little about communities in the Netherlands. And only when the government is involved, like in the case of Specific Southeast Asian community—because the government got them here. But in the case of the Caribbean Community, for example, they came here after independence so there's no government involvement really, so there's very little in the archives.

A: Right. So, the initial selection was made entirely by you?

M: Yes, because we couldn't limit ourselves to the National Heritage Institution's collection because it would not make a fair story—it would make a story that was not representative enough for the communities. So, we also included material quite a bit from other archives and collections. But that was necessary... yeah especially we included material from smaller towns in the Netherlands, because they were much more closer with these communities than these big National Heritage Institution—they have materials from this communities, from their perspective, which the National Heritage Institutions does not have.

A: Can you give me examples of these smaller towns that you were able to get some of this material from and what kind of? Yeah, but the kind of institutions, perhaps um recording this?

M: Yeah, just like city archives. But from very small towns. And they have materials that are much closer to the communities than these big National Heritage Institution. So, we asked people from the communities that where can we find the material that you want us to include and they pointed us to those archives—so that's how we did it.

A: Oh, that's really interesting. Yeah, it's also interesting that you made the initial selection because for us this is going to go online, right? And a lot of experts are going to use it, obviously, like, in that researchers who may have the methodologies and tools required to use this infrastructure. But oftentimes for non-experts, that's another question of how to make it much more accessible for them.

M: Yeah, so what I did was that I went to this archive online, then I downloaded the material, and then I put it on the Miro App. I put it on the Miro boards for people to look at and then they could respond using the chat or, you know, the post-its and write their comments and say “no, we don't want this or I'm missing this” and this is how we work. So we had to rework it and that was actually the most time consuming thing—download pictures of the document and then I used links to the National Heritage Institution so that they could see it on the National Heritage Institution website, for example....but I downloaded the material in this way...because otherwise, if you don't do it like this, they (*the communities*) cannot all work with it.

A: Yeah, this is really interesting what you did. And did you organize it by themes or how did you organize?

M: So, yah the different storylines of the the exhibition had different boards. So I let people look at certain boards relevant to their questions. And then they could also see what other people from the community responded and we would talk about it in our teams meeting or, you know,....

A: Yeah, that is a superbly interesting. How did the communities themselves receive this exhibition of yours?

M: Yeah, for them....hahah...as a curator you only hear the positive things. Yeah. But yeah what I heard was very positive because these are communities that never get too much (?) support (?). So, for them it was the first. So, yeah, then it's always a personal.

But it also worked for Muslims from other communities because it's a story they don't know and there's a lot that's common to many Muslims—like the mosque, the rituals.

A: And I see you're a heritage expert, so if you also have thoughts on other archives.... like if you've seen other archives who are doing interesting work in terms of like engaging the community or any other kinds of practices that you have thought could contribute to unsilencing voices or just meaningful structural change, that'd be really nice to hear about.

M: I think that the Archives here in the Netherlands are very open to this. Much more so than the museums. Museums, they seem to be very open—they talk a lot about decolonisation—but as institutions they are very close and very hard to collaborate with because yeah because of certain structures.

But the archives are much more open to it, but it's difficult of course for the archives because they cannot change the archives itself. You cannot add silences. Which is much easier to do in a museum.

So, add multiple voices—I would be interested in how they would do it. Yeah, but yeah, the discussion is very much alive here, also with the archivist. yeah.

A: Do you think this is a more recent phenomenon or has it been ongoing for a while?

M: No, it's recent. It's maybe five years or so. Okay.

A: Cool. I don't think I have a very much else to ask you right now, but um I think for me, the biggest thing I got out of this was particularly the Miro boards bit where, you know, that's actually one big step towards non-experts in particular accessing a lot of that material and yeah, that's really interesting. So, it's almost like you already curated something.

M: So, yeah. yeah, it was just because we didn't have a lot of time and it was because people from these communities live all over the country, so it's very difficult to get them through to the Hague during uh office hours for actual meetings. So, we decided to do it online so they can do it in the evening and then have zoom meetings.

So in this way they could still see the material, we could show it. Not the real material, but at least the digital version of it, and then have them look at the text and the photos and the documents to make a proper selection. So that's why we did that really. But yeah, it was curated in the sense that we made the preselection and then a more narrow selection based on their responses and then we added and they added things.

A: I think that's something that perhaps GLOBALISE could also kind of incorporate as a space for people to have discussions, right, about certain material. So that could be really useful. Um okay, that's it I think for now....thank you so very much....thank you. I'll keep you updated on whatever we do actually come up with. Thank you so much.

INTERVIEW 3 | Independent researcher specialising in Dutch-Maratha historical sources | Early modern Dutch paleography and colonial documentation

A: Be nice to know what you're doing on the globalize project and then we can get started.

N: Okay, sure. Yeah, Hello, I'm N. I'm working as a software engineer and also a part of the globalize project and I have joined globalize project a few months back to work as an external consultant of sorts to help with the places data date. So as with the other consultants, my job is to find the new places in various Dutch sources, and while the Dutch sources might be anything, anything is in, it maybe be a travelogue, it might be a newspaper, but I myself am primarily concentrating on the VOC archive, which have been digitized and also transcribed through the Globalise project. So, I'm using them.

And there are two ways that I go about doing it.... I'm also working in some other area, in historical research. For example, my specialties are Dutch records related to Western Indian State history. So, I know a bunch of places from Western Indian State history, so I try to see if those places have appeared in the Dutch records, with some variations in spelling, etc. So that was one way. I already know the place and I'm trying to see if it is there reflected in the Dutch records, so that is one way. Another way is to go through some related sources like, for example, consider Marcus Finks book—like Dutch missions to the Nayaka State of Madurai. So a bunch of towns in southeastern Southern Region appear and I see if those terms have already been taken care of by the project people and if not, I just try to look for them in the archive. These are the two main ways that I'm going about doing that. And so far I have managed to locate about 150 places—some from Western Region, some from Southern Region but primarily I would say it's been Western Indian State and Southern Region. Some in South-Central Region, some in Southeastern Region, in Southwestern Region and some also in the north. But primarily it's been Western Indian State and Southern Region for the time being.

A: And how exactly do you search for these places on the Globalize infrastructure?

N: I know the spellings, and how they appear. For example, they don't use they don't really use K, they mostly use C. Like, for example, for Major Eastern City or whatever, it does not really start with K. So, I use C. Then also in place of Ai, they might use Ij something or simple e... So basically, what I tried to do is convert the modern spelling into the probable Dutch spelling. So, sometimes it gives some hits, sometimes it doesn't. And then due to the limitations of transcribing, you know, OCR is mostly accurate but it can never be 100% percent accurate. So there are some mistakes. So, with experience, I know what kind of mistakes are likely to have cropped up and I try to incorporate those as well. So that the chances are better at finding the places.

N: I know Dutch. I know modern and old dutch till B1 level. I actually learnt it for historical research. I learned it for my own research project. It's been 10 years. In 2016,

- To find VOC records related to Shivaji and records about him

A: VOC archives have a lot of problematic terminology particularly. So we have to think about how people, particularly from the global South experience, read these archives? Is it triggering, you know, because at the National Heritage Institution, people break down in the reading room. So we are just thinking about what is the best way to make it a little bit safer for people to access these archives. You have a lot of experience both with the National Heritage Institution and then also the Globalize infrastructure. So it would be nice to hear about your experiences. It need not be bad. It could be positive also. But because you've also interacted with both archives, it will be nice to do a comparison and you're looking at a lot of place names, which are typically, my guess is not that problematic. But if you've also come across terminology, which is a little bit jarring, you know, uh.

N: There are problematic terms. Based on my limited experience, i've seen the 17th and 18th century. So, if there are mercantile or political rivals. For example Dutch were interacting with various Indian polities, take Western Indian State itself as an example. So, their bureaucracy was full of Brahmins, who they had to deal with on a daily basis. So the Dutch call them names and abuses—I saw something like that. Like “Bad (Cord) Brahmin.” But I didn't find it triggering. This is part and parcel of records—whether European or Western Indian State Records.

But if someone's background is problematic/sensitive, for example., if someone is from and Southeast Asian Community or Caribbean Community background and some ancestor of theirs was brought as a slave, then I understand that they could break down. Or if someone is from a tribal community, and there might be unsavoury words about them. But this goes. These were different times, and we should not be that surprised if they use those words.

A: Yeah, I understand what you are saying, but I think also as an academic, it's a little bit more that we have the context. But this archive is going to be used by everyday user. So, that's something we could do, like give a context—like this is true of all records. So that is something that we could give a context about so that people walk into it knowing that what to expect so to say. So that's one possibility. But if you can think of other like strategies that we could adopt, then like especially with regards to unsavoury terms with regards slavery or just tribal communities, etc. I think there, in some of those situations, perhaps we can also have like some sort of trigger warning that you're going to now enter a space. But yeah, if you have other thoughts, it would be lovely to hear.

N: So, for example, platforms like Facebook or X have trigger warnings when something is very violent or sexually inappropriate. Or we can make a glossary of triggering terms in which you have terms categorised by region, or caste, or gender. Even in terms of unsavoury terms, we must also categorise and hierarchise, given that some unsavoury terms are more likely to sting—you could do a pilot study.

But are non-academic people really using GLOBALISE to a large extent.

A: I think the hope is that they ultimately will. So, a new community outreach person has joined the team and her entire job is to take this infrastructure to all kinds of audiences in all parts of the world. So once they go public in one-two years, then they are hoping that you know all kinds of people use it.

N: Yeah, but it is already public. I think they might do more publicity, exactly. I believe to not have sensitive terms from that period itself is an anomaly.

A: What has been your general experience using the Globalize infrastructure, do tell me about that.

N: Terrific. I do though have some suggestions on how to improve its accessibility:

Delpher.nl---Website for Dutch periodicals and newspapers. The navigation on this vs on Globalise, if you compare. So on both I am required to use keywords to search. But Delpher can be more specific in that it asks if I want to search in books, or periodicals or newspapers. I understand that GLOBALISE'S nature is different. So leave that. But once, say, if you restrict that to newspapers, you can further restrict the terms to 1600-1650 for instance. Custom range in terms of years is something that is lacking in GLOBALISE. In GLOBALISE, the global term is used, and at best you can separate them by volumes, but that is still not that handy, especially if I want to find it in custom years. Every volume has a year, alright, so indirectly I can figure it out. But directly it is a bit of a hassle.

Two, suppose we look at India. And in India, the most is written about Major Port City, Eastern Region, Coastal Region and Eastern Coastal Region. Now it is not true or necessary that in a record on Major Port City, Coastal Region is not mentioned. However, even if the heading is Major Port City, how would that look. Example: I want to look for textile trade in the environment of Major Port City 1720-1740. Now ideally, I should get the volumes related to Major Port City and in the date range. Pinpointed in navigation.

Now if you look at a 17th c volume — first there is an index, then title, number of pages. Above title there will be a section title—Major Port City or Coastal Region. So when I am searching, I want to be able to search just under Major Port City. It may be mentioned under Coastal Region too, but that is not what I want access to. So if such pinpointed research can be enabled, that would be incredible. They already have that facility in some way, so enabling those functions would be great.

A third point—in these volumes, there are reports right. Now in these reports there may be another category of documents. For example, if there is a report that an official is sending to his boss about Coastal Region, which is accompanied by letters with the Maharajas of Coastal Region for instance. So for example if there is a search term (of interest) that I want to find in the letters exchanged with the local princes, is there a way to distinguish between the term in the report vs the letters. This may be a long shot because.

And then for example, in the 17th century volumes, (this has nothing to do with GLOBALISE, but the nature of the records), it has a folio number on the top right. But not every volume or page has that. But there are entire volumes without folio numbers. Nature of 18th c volumes – categorised by region. There may thus be a folio number 10 for Major Port City and for Coastal Region, etc, which therefore does not lead to a unique page. And it is difficult to locate.

That has to do with the nature of the record so what can GLOBALISE do. But at most, what they can do is ask, do you want this page number for Major port City or for Coastal Region.

For the 14,900 some volumes, half have been made digital and the rest have not been digitised. I understand that has to do with funding. But the rest would also be great. Current digitised volumes have to do with political history, it does not have payroll data and such. But even this is good.

What is great about GLOBALISE is that unlike British archives which are all proprietary, GLOBALISE is not.

A: Last, I see you have the technical knowledge, like you have the methodology, you are a proper historian. But how do you think somebody with no such, you know, technical knowledge can navigate through GLOBALISE. Like you even have an understanding of the structure of the archives itself, right? So, that's seemingly important information to have to make a globalized useful. What do we do for people who have no such technical knowledge? What would your ideas.

N: Well you can't do very much. That is my short answer. Because you definitely need knowledge of Dutch. You need an idea about what one is looking for—from which region for some instance. You need knowledge, to navigate the archives.

At best, to learn some old Dutch, you can have resources or a page on Dutch palaeography—like a basic course. Like this letter is written such, or it has these kind of abbreviations, or exceptions. Some videos for instance.

There are other existing resources. Like a VOC glossorium with terms that recur in the VOC archives. And then a dictionary—open internet.dictionary online. So if we can include the links of these resources, that would be great.

And if people want to check about their own region, then, you can have an example video of doing that kind of research. Like my researching Western Indian State history, and the obstacles I faced, and how I resolved that. Or someone is from Southeast Asia, or elsewhere. Case studies would help.

A: Other infrastructures that you have particularly been impressed by.

N: Cali.cf. There are portraits and the like in this well.

A: Thank you so much. You've really thought about a lot of it and I really appreciate that. If have any other follow-up questions, I will write to you if you don't mind. And maybe if we decide to make a video.

N: This person is actually from an indigenous community, so it would be good to talk to them as well

A: Thank you so much, N. Have a wonderful day, thank you. Bye. Bye.

INTERVIEW 4 | Community Manager at National Archival Institution, Exhibition Maker | Heritage accessibility, collaborative storytelling, and inclusive archival outreach

A: Should I quickly give you an introduction about myself and then maybe you can do the same? That'd be really lovely.

S: Yes.

A: So um my name is A and I currently work on something called the Globalize project where they are creating a digital infrastructure whereby they are digitizing five million pages of the VOC archives. And basically, since they're going to be taking this infrastructure public very soon we're really thinking about the best way to enable access to it, particularly in a way, which is the least triggering for the audience, particularly people from erstwhile colonized spaces. So I thought, and we already did chat about this briefly and it seems like you at the National Heritage Institution do have to deal with a lot of sensitive material, which could potentially be offensive. F was telling me about how, you know, oftentimes people break down in the reading rooms. So, I wanted to hear from you, um, you know, what are some of the strategies that you already implement at the National Heritage Institution or even are thinking about, you know, you might have seen practices in other spaces with respect to, you know, enabling access in a fashion, which is safe for the user. So, it would be lovely to hear your thoughts on that. And I'm an anthropologist by training, so a lot of this project for me, this research is based on, you know, talking to people, thinking about how they experience the archives and therefore, you know, how we could do things differently. So, yeah, that's that about me.

S: Okay. Well, I think the main thing I've done at the archives until now is making the archives more accessible to different kinds of target groups by means of exhibitions, education, and workshops and other programs. So, it's not the regular way to access the archives...from the perspective of the archives

So, what we've done last few years is inviting people and groups to help us, accessing the archives in a different way. Now we've worked together with a Slavery Museum, for example, and we've made an exhibition about slavery history from our archives, but mostly from people from nowadays, what are their perspectives and what's the meaning of the archives for them nowadays?

And our educational programs always try to convey the personal histories that lie within the archives. So not so much from the facts of history because that would represent a lot of colonial perspectives, but more like how was that for the persons who lived in those days? And what can you learn from it and how does it affect your life? We always look for the different point of view in the archives and trying to translate that to stories that are comprehensible and understandable and relating to the people that nowadays. So that's what we did with our products for the public.

And one of those things is that we were asked to participate in called "Family History Workshop," and Family History is a workshop, especially developed for students and younger people with a Southeast Asian background. And that was initially initiated and developed by YK, but there are more initiatives to help the young people to find their roots,

to find answers to their questions in a safe space. So, there was a workshop for not such a large group about maximum of 30 persons. And if Y would then accompany those students and tell them what they can expect and tell them how to do research and also provide a little context sort of lecture so that they were prepared to dive into the archives and make their own personal stories. And she asked me and my team to help her with that because our archives are such a huge resource, very important sources for finding your roots. And so that taught me a lot about when people do research in the archives that they sometimes need to be supported to be well, you know, yeah, you just get a little context and those kinds of things.

And that is also how we developed our exhibitions lately. So not from the point of view of the National Heritage Institution and from the perspective of power, but more the perspective of people nowadays, what do they feel? What do they need? What do they think is important and how do they commit? How do they read the archives? So that's what we've been trying to do.

A: Can you give me an example, perhaps of one such exhibition and then how you are actually incorporating these more contemporary perspectives, so to say, that would be lovely, just, yeah.

S: Yeah, one of the first exhibitions we worked in that way was an exhibition about Caribbean Island. It started as an assignment to make an exhibition about the West Indian company, so not the VOC, but the WIC. But it was an assignment that was really focused on those documents, on those archives, and on that company. And then my team said, "no, we're not going to do that because then you have the colonial perspective." And it's more like an exhibition that tells you about facts and figures, which are always from the colonial perspective.

But then we had a brainstorm together and we thought, no, what we need to show is what do those archives mean nowadays. The WIC is mainly responsible for present day societies in in the Caribbean and also in Caribbean Community, there's a lot of influence of those archives still tangible. And we thought which country is very important place for that history, and we came up with the Isle of Caribbean Island because it has such a variety of people living there and such a well, it's a history that's closely related to the WIC archives. And Caribbean Island is still related to the kingdom of the Netherlands. So we thought it would be interesting to dive into that history and see how the people of Caribbean Island are nowadays still related to that history. How are they still related to that history? And we asked a curator, and she has roots from Caribbean Island and she developed the exhibition together with us, so the themes and what But she didn't want to do that without people of Caribbean Island.

So, we also worked very closely together with the archives as Local Archive and with the archaeological institutes and with an educator from Caribbean Island and a photographer from Caribbean Island, and also interviewed people from there. And so, we put together all the elements and made it into one story. So, it was really like a perspective of a lot of Caribbean Islandpeople looking back on history. And that made a very, very interesting for us because when certain details of history came to the surface that otherwise would not be discovered. And the most important thing, that's why it was a great success in my point of

view, is that young people here in the Netherlands who have a background from Caribbean Island were amazed by all these histories. They never knew of. They were very proud that finally an institute like the National Heritage Institution told their history, but that was very important to know that that that we succeeded in doing that. And they and they felt strengthened by that history and they felt like their identity became a little better known to them. So that was really like the big success to me that the young people here so it helped their identity.

A: I can totally understand that and that's really quite lovely and in fact it was going to be my follow-up question and I think you're already answering it as we speak. But um I really like that, you know, instead of the archives in their raw form, so to say, the medium is exhibitions or workshops and the like, right? And wherein you're bringing different people together and getting perspectives of people from for instance, Caribbean Island and presenting a story which is much more relatable today. And so I just wanted to understand, you know, like, what are the benefits you're seeing in these mediums as opposed to say, for instance, somebody just going, looking up the National Heritage Institution, the digital archives, so to say, or going to the reading room, you know, versus presenting the narrative in a fashion, which is much more nuanced or taking into account multiple perspectives. So,because I really like this idea of exhibitions and I definitely think we can do some of that as well, but I'm also thinking, you know, how do we make it safer when people are just like browsing through the Globalize archive on their own, you know? Like, if there are all these sensitive terms and like there you spoke really about Family History Workshop like that that I was thinking is so interesting if we can provide something like a tool kit for people, right? Like first context, obviously, but also how to look at the archives. So, if you have thoughts on that as well, that would be so lovely.

S: YK, she already...I think it would be interesting for you to talk to her because she also made ait's not a game....but it's like a set of cards that ask your questions, so they can help you uh work with the archives. But for us, it's always a balance in helping people search in the archives, but without telling them exactly what to do, otherwise you you direct them too much.

Yeah, and I think a very important for Family History Workshop is that when you start searching and when you start looking in the archive into very sensitive history, then it's very important that you have people around you who have already had that experience. So, they can help you and they can support you and I think that's the main goal of Family History Workshop. That is something that the National Heritage Institution is not necessarily ready for. So we need people like Y to help us in that direction. I'm not sure if not answer the question. Um yeah, can you repeat this person's name as well for me? YK. And she developed Family History Workshop so that's the brand name as well. Got it. And you have a connection with her? Yes, I can connect you together. I'll do that.

A: Yeah, that would be fantastic. Yeah. I think my question was that in the realm of like exhibitions and workshops and in person events, so to say, it seems like the National Heritage Institution are beginning to do really interesting work in, you know, interpreting the archives from multiple perspectives. But I was wondering if there are strategies that you have also thought about or implemented when it comes to people just browsing through the digital archives itself without any support, so to say.

S: There are no strategies as far as I know, No, no, no. No, as far as I know, there are no strategies. But we did have a project that was called Language and Context. Language technology/ terminology and context that looked at the search terms and there's a little trigger warning on the website that you might encounter with respect to terms that are racial or discriminatory. But it's not a project that has been developed completely, so we do have certain tools to help you, but not really like you describe it. There's not a strategy at this moment. not overall strategy.

A: But already the trigger warning contextualization, I think is already a really good start, you know. Yeah. And coming back more to the exhibitions and workshops, you know, it would be just lovely for me to hear other examples that you thought were really quite successful. Like you got a very good response from the participants, if there are any other projects that you had that be great to hear about.

S: Yes, when we developed the Caribbean Island exhibition, we've had a beautiful cooperation with the Caribbean ancestry club. And that is a society for young people from the Caribbean to come together and to create some kind of safe space for them. We've done some programs for them.

But lately we've done an exhibition with the Muslim archives.. Maybe you've seen it when you here. And that was developed by two people who work for the Muslim archives. And, I offered them 100 square meters for an exhibition because they don't have the building, they don't have a space, they don't have a way to communicate in a visual manner. So, I offer them an exhibition space and they develop these exhibitions with the team and from the archives. And K, he is one of the persons. He also used the exhibition to develop programs for his community. They used the archives for their community. So that was that was really something very special, and I think it was highly appreciated and it's just that now that the exhibition is finished, then suddenly there is no corporation. We have to find a way from the archives to keep in touch with them, you know, otherwise, it's just a temporary aid, but I would really like to be more of a platform for them to be able to do programs from the archives. And that is something there is there's no strategy yet, so once the exhibition finished, our corporation finished, and I think that's really a shame of all the effort and all the things we achieved. So that is something that should really developed.

A: Yeah, that's a really fantastic idea.

S: I think when you look at the VOC archives, the Muslim archives could be a partner to work together with how you open up VOC archives for people of their community, so that will be someone you can talk to as well.

A: Yeah, again, it'd be lovely if you have a connection there if you could facilitate that. That would be amazing, yeah, yeah.

S: And so that's how I contributed my department to opening up the archive. In short? I really.

A: Yeah. Yeah, that sounds really wonderful, honestly. I don't really have any more questions per se. I will do my own um research a little bit more into perhaps some of the programs and exhibitions you have had. But yeah, I think this is already a really, really good start to think about enabling safer access to our own research infrastructure.

S: And I see that you are connected with the Maritime museum, because right now they have an exhibition now on slavery history, which is curated by DB who also curated our Caribbean Island exhibition. So, I think she could be a very interesting person to connect with.

A: Yeah, that'd be fantastic. So yeah, so maybe I can just write to you after this with the three people you mentioned.

S: um for Family History Workshop. uh they are all working for themselves, so I'm not sure if they are willing to just um yeah, I work for the ali, so my time is is uh abundant. But they are all um working for themselves, so I'm not sure how but but you have to figure that out again. That's fine. I'm willing to take the risk if they agree all the better if they don't, then that's also fine. Yeah. Cool. Thank you so much. um I'm going to think with what you've said and if I do have any follow-up questions, maybe I'll write to you or if um, yeah, you're open to another short call at a later point that'd be great. Yeah, a project we're also working on from the archives, but this way of looking to the ars is still in being developed from the. So I'm very interested in your research and the outcomes of your research. Yeah, please let's keep touch. Let's keep in touch. I'm definitely happy to keep you up updated and I think we are working. We have some affiliations with the National Heritage Institution as well, the globalized projects. So I'll definitely keep in touch. Yeah.. Thank you so very much. You're welcome. and I'll check the three people that we talked about and see if they're willing to give them your email address, so they can see if they want to get contact with you. And then you can just make arrangements with them. That sounds fantastic. Yes, okay. Thank you so much and wishing you a lovely year., you too. Thank you. All right. talk soon. bye. Talk soon. bye. Bye.

INTERVIEW 5 | Graduate student in Design Program | Graphic design background, performative art responses to colonial violence and institutional critique

J: I don't remember if you were there the whole time.

A: I wasn't unfortunately, there the entire time, which is why, like, I would know a lot more if I'd stayed but I had other engagements, but yeah, so like today, I would like to hear about everything, like your project, and, yeah, all the context around it, but also, like what you spoke about at the panel, I briefly heard what you had to say. And I definitely, like, instantly, was like, Okay, this sounds so, so relevant, to my work.

J: So, where to start this? This is, like the whole year project. I think this year has been very tough in in the way, because a lot of our projects start relating with archives and archives from the Netherlands, and as maybe you hear, none of my classmates are from here. So it was very hard for us to go into archive and feel it was something we needed to talk about it, or that it will represent somehow our history. I was also telling you we were having this collaboration with globalize, with another class, and also, like, start navigating this platform, — was very weird for us in the sens. I mean, not because it's a bad platform, but is more because you have, like, all this digital information. And the good thing is that we can translate it, if we go to chatGPT or whatever, but it was a lot like you get lost in the idea of these digital books, and it only started making sense for us when we were able to go to the archive and ask for these books and have it in our hands. And I think there was a lot of what the material and the decay of the material that could talk to us. For example, there's something that, for me, was very important, like seeing the sign, for example, of whoever was doing the inventory. And probably this person was very rough, so it was like, very hard, like the sign, the signature was like tough, and it was what the paper was breaking. So, for me it was the metaphor of his own toughness is making him disappear from the Archive. So, these things that you can can't feel in the digital space came real when we were with the documents,

And at the moment, both of my research start to be connected with nature, and the idea of how nature was captive. I was using a map, because the map I was searching, was in South American Region 1, and it was like this long scroll, like when you open it you have to scroll several times to see from the beginning to the end. And for me, was overwhelming, because it was just lines of green and it was not a presentation of real nature. And then I saw this other map of other plantations in the area, and you see, like all these blocks of land separating the river from nature, from the wild nature, let's say, and I start feeling like, oh my god, this was really like a camp that they were building around nature. And in the Globalize project, we were researching about green fields, on the standardization and naming of a lot of plants and creating like this greed. And all the time we were feeling like this was the moment of the creation of the greed and how we still live in this greed, and how to escape it was— it was impossible, basically. And so, the archive, the project, directly with the National Heritage Institution, for me, became very personal as the way, the introduction of the project, we were there, and I have this since I am in the master I'm always thinking on feelings as a way of. Research and the way of how people react to different situations give us a lot of, let's say, information to then approach them in a different way, or let feelings talk can be also like another way of explaining my projects, I did something like this, interviewing some woman in politics in South American Country 1, where I come from, and it was not them talking, but it

was their feelings talking —where they were located in the body, because they represent different things depending where they are located. So, I had like this idea when I came there, and I was, like, very into understanding how they analyse feelings, or if they were recollecting this data? And the answer was no. Most of all, in that moment, we were talking about this condition that was for kids, and they were explaining, I was like, it's very hard to take, like, this data of the kids, if the parents are not there, blah, blah, blah. And it was like, okay, if you say so, okay.

And then it was introduction that is actually the co author of one of the last books of the archive. And the way he started speaking and describing this map was, like, I had this moment in which I was like, maybe it's my problem. I'm understanding something wrong. Also, for those days, we were reading a lot of different teachers from the Netherlands even that are rethinking the way of using language to describe certain content and to try to change the atmosphere around history and then space, where I thought was the place where things are changing and then going through this violent language and also seeing that this person after we say something we didn't acknowledge even it was like, I mean, I feel he was looking at me and not understanding why I was so uncomfortable. And then I literally flowed into crying and he never approached me or say if there was something wrong some other people of the archive, did. But eight months later, I have never had like any further connection or conversation with him.

I don't know if I want to right now, for example, because I think I've been open to conversations with a lot of people in the archive, and also the performance that they have includes this story. Because I want people to know that it's not just work. It has a big impact, and it's not because it was my...in the text, I talk about the ancestors of my land, and I'm not saying this as they were actually my family, because that is just this human feeling of feeling, of feeling what other people might have felt. That for me, is important. And so my project, my project in the archive, is about bringing people to cry into the archive, because I feel we haven't made like the proper mourning of this era and we just keep going as if it was nothing but there is a lot of pain behind them. Still, we can feel it these days. For me, it was important to mobilize these feelings in order to change the perception we have on colonization?

A: Yeah, I have quick question. So, couple of questions. So, thank you very much. That's really a good start to like, giving me an insight, but it'd be nice to also like, because I'm really, like coming in blind, like I've met O and I've kind of understood what your program is about, but it would be good to hear from you what program you're part of, and then why you guys were engaging with the National Heritage Institution, for starters. But also, you were talking about this introduction that was given to you into these archives early on. So, what like, if you can give me an example of some of the language that may have been used, and how it made you feel personally. You have already touched on this, but like, if you can elaborate upon it for me a little bit more. The next question would also be like, did all your classmates experience this, like, similarly, was everybody, like, put off by the language, or was it much more true for certain kinds of social location, like dependent and influenced by where you're coming from. So that'd be a little bit nice to hear about. Yeah.

J: Okay, so I'm doing this program called Design Program. I think if you ask to whoever, everyone will give you like different answers of what it means to be in this program. My short

understanding of it is design, art based that comes together with research and journalism with a critical political view, through just a lot of things, through a lot of situations, political situations that we're going through right now. And that also means looking back and how, I think it's important for us, how we narrate all these stories, and how we created these perceptions, and where people get tuned to this story, so we use different medium.

I come from a background of graphic design and communication, working a lot in politics and activism and education for democracy and women participation, young people participation in democracy. So that's more my background, and I come here, and I start developing more like my artistic practice. That was something I was not very tuned with, and it's something that I am doing and starting to go to this idea of performing, that I have more like this performatic act, which means maybe having some movements and embodiment of feelings. I use Latin American myths of women in order to represent these feelings and visualization as a shelter, as a way of calling my ancestry, as a way of not feeling too alone in a world that maybe is not mine, or a territory that is not mine, that is here. So I bring all this power into my body to feel, let's say brave to talk about these topics. So that's being right now my practice, we start this collaboration, basically because the program decided, I think no one of us will start with National Heritage Institution. For me, it wasn't also not like an easy like, I was not imagining I will go and knock into the National Heritage Institution, like, Hey, can I see your stuff? I was really excited. I can share with you the text of my performance, if you want, because I explain a little bit more what happened that day, other things. And I was really excited. I mean, for me, this was having an opportunity in my life that I never imagined.

I was in during the summer in the archive in European City 2. I mean, there. I mean, for me, that archive is more emotional, like I felt that every word of the things that I was reading was like, very harsh in me. And I even went to the church where Christopher Columbus is buried, and I just wanted to be there to say, like, I really hate you really did very terrible things. I can't believe, like, this infrastructure to "rest in peace". I don't, I don't think you are so. And also, like, this emotional heaviness didn't allow me at the moment to go and understand, how can I approach to those documents, and maybe I'm not ready to go to this direct history, but I was there and trying to understand a little bit. And then I escaped and came back to continue with the National Heritage Institution.

And so, yes, it was, I think a lot of the process of this project was on finding positionality, how we all find positionality in a history that at first, we believe is not ours. And. And through all the experiences each one of us was finding this positionality. And for me, it's clear that it's not the history of the Netherlands, that it is part of the history of the world and the implications it had all around, so that's why it's OUR history.

Regarding how people reacted I mean...I'm trying not to use the words he was saying, but he was referring, basically he used, like, the N word to describe the people portrayed in this map. And also, he like, he wouldn't say like people who were seeking freedom, but he was maybe saying people escaping. And then he described how they were on fire, because they are on fire on the map and the way.... And the way he described it for me was like terrific [terrifying]. And right now, I have mixed ideas, because at the I had this talk with some of my teachers—one is from Jamaica, the other one is from Middle Eastern country. And so, they helped me process. They were trying to reframe and redescribe what we were seeing that it lands in a different way. At that moment, I was also with two mates—one of them actually

also cried, but not a public way. She went to the toilet and cry for a bit there and like came back again to what was happening. And after several conversations, I now understand that there was more people that was feeling like very uneasy and comfortable feeling also this shame, like a lot of emotions were going in the moment. But I think I was the one who explodes, and it showed immediately. So it also become like, yeah, I was the picture, but everyone, like a lot of people, behind me, was also having kind of this struggle. Because I even remember that in this conversation, I was thinking, like, I hate Europeans. That was like my headline, let's say. And then having this conversation, and I was saying this girl from Portugal and this guy from Italy, struggling with the same that I was a struggle, trying to support me, trying to make me feel welcome and understood. And then I was also saying that, okay, no, I'm falling into this game of discrimination and violence. This is not the European, it's just the people who, now I can describe us, that have like this colonial admiration. They are not willing to recognize or acknowledge a lot of the things that happened in the past. Also when I was like, in this crying session, there was a school group, it's in between 10 and 12 years probably, they were gonna see this new exhibition that we saw. And the first video is showing how people were transported in this huge ships from Africa to the Americas. And, like, this illustration and how they were put, like, very packed in, in these boats. And this kid started, like, feeling dizzy, and he was about to throw up. And like, they have to take him to the nursery, for example. And by seeing this kid, I was also, I was like, 'Okay, it's not only me.' So I also start to feel a little bit more chill, even though I was worried, because it was, it was a little... but then I started understanding, like, this is this not only me. There's like, just some people that is showing the feeling that is in between all of us and that, for me, was very interesting to... I use also the story of the kid, because it was a kid from the Netherlands. Maybe he doesn't know all the things that I know. He's just starting this journey, but have like the same reaction, and is where I found, like this human feeling of, I think, is beyond empathy, or, yeah, like not understanding, how come we can be as Human, so violent. So yes,

A: And what was your final art piece? Sorry, I don't know which one was yours, and if I saw it.

J: I can also send you some pictures. Create this character based on one Latin American myth. I didn't create her. I mean, she exists. I just was giving her a shape in relation with this map I was studying. So I create this costume in order for me to use the costume in the space a lot of the distance I have with the archive is that I feel that it's a place that people don't inhabit, that people go and take away stuff, but it's an empty space for me when it's lack human connection. So I had this character, and my performance was more like..I was calling it like a walking performance, or, let me remember, because I'm still trying to define what is I am doing. It was a performative walk. Let's say. So, I start talking and telling all this story of what happened in the archive and how I felt, where I come from, who's la Giona? Why is represented in this art piece of mine? And I also make a critique to this exploitation of land and how institutions are trying to erase a lot of the knowledge that we already have that come from our connection with our own territories. And it was also like a performance of resistance to this institutional structures. And so I have this costume. I start by, like, pulling people into the space and have like a little in Spanish is called aquatizar, which is mean, which means, like, when you land in water, okay, specific name in the text, you will see it as becoming water, because it has no translation. And I want, in the beginning, people to feel like to have the feeling when you cry and you feel like heavy and your eyes are itchy. So I

have, like this little exercise to people to feel like this, and then I start telling the story of what was my interaction with the National Heritage Institution and what things make me feel uncomfortable and make me cry? Yeah, I talk about La Gorona. So La Gorona...the meaning is crying woman. And it's a myth that is reproduced almost in every country in Latin America. That's also something very special. The original regional story before the Spanish settlers start changing it was about this woman that will cry to tell her community... she was crying because she knew, like all her descendants, meaning kids and nature were about to be destroyed. Violence was coming. So she was crying because of this. And then the colonizers changed the story, saying that it was this woman that end up having kids with a Spanish, soldier. And then she felt like regret, because it was against her community somehow, and she killed her own kids, drowning them in the river. And that's why she was always crying to the river. And there are, like, a lot of different stories based on this and she became this monster of the forest, and whatever, whatever.

So there's a lot of people trying to give like this other look of what La Gorona represents. And also it's aware of how this story is controlling like the body of women, and how we are only the mothers, or there's a lot of things that for me are important in the things that I do.

And this idea of crying as a way of cleaning, as a way of showing, as a way of making people feel uncomfortable here in this country because people don't know how to interact with other people that they don't know. This idea of someone is crying in front of you and is kind of asking for this help or for this companion, and how will people react? And so for me, it's also at the end, I ask people to write down they have, like this long papers, if people want to add some more stories that will be also sorrow by La Gorona. And eventually I would like to add part of those stories to this costume, because this costume is like, a lot of stripes, like, it's a heavy costume, and they have some words that come from my story. But then I would like to have more words from other people's stories, so that these words move. And the reason why is, like these long stripes of green fabric is because I imagine I will take like this map that is so with a lot of green stripes, and I will use those to dress myself and give like bring back the meaning and the narratives to this space that was emptied when they put a plantation.

My way of closing for myself. I'll send you a write up—some pictures and text.

A: Yes, that would be great. And what map did you personally deal with? And then like, did they like prepare you with any like methods or like with context before you went in because you're a graphic designer by training. You know, like, oftentimes when historians go in they're given a lot of context, they're given a lot of methods, not that that saves them from any of the violence, but it kind of primes them or they know what they might confront. So is that something you guys got before going in?

J: It's crazy, because actually this introduction was the way of preparing us before seeing the maps. Yeah. So, I mean, we were reading as I was telling you, we were reading like his name is (?). He's a teacher at University. So we were reading a little bit of him. We were reading, sorry, I'm super bad with names. Oh, my God. And academic reference. She also have like, text on archives and what it means an archive and infrastructure versus the hegemonic archive, like all these things read about her. We were having like this approach through theory and reading people that were working in the field, that was kind of helping us

land into it. But the big introduction was going to be that one. We also, like, during that day, we were also reviewing all the maps and understanding different parts of the map, the navigation, like a lot of things. And then after this was in March and in May, we have, like, a knowledge day, and with other people working with archives, and it was in the Research Institute, and we were talking with the people of ?, and I don't know, like two initiatives in the Research Institute that like help us, but we had like, big, big moment of confrontation, like all the time. There was something of that day that even though there were people feeling like me, there was I have, like the example of one of my classmates, that she approached me and she asked me genuinely, like, I don't understand why you're feeling so... why is being the this impactful for you? She asked me, on a way, not because she didn't believe it or whatever, because she felt like no connection. And when I started like pointing out these things, she was like, Okay, well, now I understand. Now, I recognize this other part that I was kind of blinded. And when we talk about this several months later, she also changed a little bit of the way she thinks. And she says, like, because of this situation, I understand several other things. And that's also, for me, very important, because I'm trying to build this bridge between the colonial north and the colonized south, and right now, I mean, in this, in this gap moment, because the people who wrote things, for example, in my piece, are all people who come from the Americas, Latin America, and the Caribbean. Let's say I have conversations with people from Europe, and they like, I could see how they were affected by what I was saying. And I saw like, wet eyes, like about to cry, but they don't write anything. The Americas wrote something. So there's also, like, I still need to understand how I can make this bridge with them. And I think it's a matter also of positionality, like they don't want to overtake a space.

A: So you think that's why they did not write.

J: I feel they don't feel comfortable also of giving evidence of their vulnerability..

A: Interesting. Yeah.

J: Because they tell me things. And yeah, and like it moves people and like I can tell how in the movement or in the archives when I'm talking for some people that feel very uncomfortable and try to make distance, but they don't leave. It's not a short walk. It's 17 mins. They stay. So they are interested in understanding what is happening. But then the final part is like there is no evidence... one person in the archive, like random person, I was doing a rehearsal, and this man who was like 70, and he looked at me and he said like, are you protesting? and I was like, actually, yes, this is it to the history here. And he was like, okay. And then I thought he was going to say something more or maybe something rude or I don't know when he said, like, can I take your picture? And it was like, yeah, sure. And he took a picture and he left.

A: Yeah. And O was telling me that your cohort decided that you all wanted to present at the National Heritage Institution itself. Is that true?

J: No. We had to present at the National Heritage Institution. The plan was to present first at a gallery exhibition thing and then the pieces will be moved to the National Heritage Institution for more weeks. But our decision was actually not having the exhibition outside of the National Heritage Institution.

A: Okay, why did you make that decision?

J: Now we are considering taking these artworks and presenting them in another space? But it had like a very important meaning that the first place where we said all the things that we wanted to say was in the heart of the National Heritage Institution. So now that it was said there, that it was born there, it can move away and spread a lot of things. Another decision that we had for the exhibition was not showing the maps. I mean, when you go through this maps and if you are translated, you will find it in like a lot of this, for example, violent language or by itself, it's in a specific story and it's the story that is still very violent and that shows like this separation. It's an instrument to other still different communities. And actually, if I think this is a graphic designer, it is very, really on this project make us question like why are we graphic designers. Like the VOC was the first designing documents and propaganda and all these things, and it's like we are in the middle of this or how our pieces of work then become like instruments of violence. So it questions a lot of our practice, and that's also very tough.

A: I have one more question for you. You, from what I understand, when you broke down, you got a lot of support for instance, from your peers, of course, and your friends, but also particularly from like your teachers, one from Middle Eastern country, one from the Caribbean? It seems like their positionality also allows them to understand what you were going through and respond to that. But um what do you think the National Heritage Institution itself could have done in that moment, you know, or any sort of any archives you know, to not make you feel the way that you did. In a way, like it could be that we change the wordings of the archives altogether. I'm not particularly for that say for instance, because I think that you also start hiding violence that happen in the past. But like you said, like that man who was doing the introduction, he saw the breaking down, and he still didnt even come to the comfort, he didn't do any. So like, that's like one basic thing he could have done. But like what else do you think are potential strategies for people like you and me or even a Dutch child who are going to encounter this violent material.

J: I really think that there should be people trained or with abilities to understand this emotional struggles and so that we can take out all these things. It it's like going to a quick therapy kind of you know. It's something that a psychologist should do rather than it be a responsibility of people of the educational team. Even they encounter violence.

A: For example?

J: The educational team of the archive so it's S, who is the person I spoke to a lot. He was on the panel. And he was actually the person from the National Heritage Institution that stayed in the conversation when it was with my teachers. There was another woman and she quit the project. She is Dutch. She also, I remember when she was talking to me that her eyes were like wet, like she was about to cry and she was holding herself. And she didn't knew how to approach me and she was understand if I was okay. And in this process I also started thinking like I don't want people to feel bad. But it is important to me. So it was a negotiation, let's say. I think I talked to like six or seven different people from the archives and they all have this moment in which their voice like cracks because they were not prepared. I think we are lacking of this emotional a strength to go and just hold someone

else, you know. I think this is just like a reflection of things that happen outside of the archive. [Inaudible] that's horrible. Like I will try to go and help.

No. Yeah, and I mean, I was thinking like the archives need a department where people can go and support the people and like have this conversation and ask for... I think by telling this story over and over, they have identified the problems and they are trying to change and they are trying to be more I think after this, there were like we really need to introduce this dictionary which was like a book about why this language really shouldn't be used. Because yeah, it's violent towards certain communities or whatever. So this actions might help but I was at some point, I was telling them like, we just opened a lot of documents of the second World War. And there people here coming every day for these documents, and it's very, very sensible, like you can see how people come in this so vulnerably, but they are trying to find their family. I have experienced in South American Country 1. I mean, this is an active process, people looking in archives to find families and took this the war somehow. And now this is happening here and there person need of conversation is not something that people can do alone. In South American Country 1 we are even public talks in which the victim and the victimizer are in the same space. And they ask for forgiveness and then the other person can say, I don't forgive you or I do forgive you, and it's a lot of emotion. And you feel also uncomfortable at times when you see that someone say, I don't forgive you. It's also hard, but atleast its happening the conversation and it's like a way of processing all the emotions and feeling that were hidden and unsilenced. So I think that that's what is missing. Like someone prepared for this. Also like in the archive they internal struggles with this. Like for me, it's very crazy how there's not like a psychologist. Because every time and this I have heard from people working there, like every time I open, anything in the archive, I might find something that may shock me. No, because of it violence. And actually, every time I go there and I open whatever document, I have like this moment I understanding processing oh my God, this is again tough. When can I just open and see something easy. That's not the case. And I don't understand actually how they deal all the time with all these things. Like some of them have like escaping areas inside of the archive, okay, and this comes more from like personal conversations I had with them. One of my classmates make his map and mapping exercise and they then to like looking up like these areas in which we see it and we kind of sleep and have this moment of needing to process without talking to other people for example. That's also super crazy.

A: No, that's crazy. And I want to ask you about your interaction with the globalize infrastructure and you were saying, you know, it's like so overwhelming, like you write one word, and have like 15,000 results. So can you speak a little bit more about like the globalize infrastructure and how you experienced that. You already touched a little bit on that but if you could elaborate maybe, that would be awesome.

And then the second question would be like we just spoke about strategies that potentially are feasible and can be done particularly in physical archives. But like if you have thoughts on how to do that in a digital space because now people are going to be able to have access to this information in their houses. And I am certain a lot of people are going to use it to look for the family.

J: I don't know. I mean, I don't have like super fresh my relationship with GLOBALISE. I understand how the tool has made information more accessible. But for me, the language

barrier was very, very hard. I don't remember because at the moment I was thinking about like changes in the user interface, especially if you are not a historian and don't easily understand stuff. It is harder to enter into this categorisation. And how we can visualize that. Like if you see like a picture of the book and then you go inside that and to the information, then it might be easier to connect because you don't understand they mentions, you don't understand that is heavy. I think I have a video also of me and one of my classmates, like interacting with one of these books because we were trying to think on what is the choreography that you do when you open this, how you need to use all of your body and how it's actually heavy and it's a metaphor that history is heavy. And so other ways of approaching that are completely different when it's like this digital cloud we don't see. I think that's the difficult part of digitalizing; yes would give more access to people that are far away and it's easier to translate because atleast with translation, I could read a language of another person.. So it's like a kind of hand like how they work together. that makes it more power so. The only thing I can think of the digital, atmosphere about, uh, how you can help people is literally having like a live chat, you know, where people can ask these things. And I also think, for example, having also a video on how to use the tool since the beginning. Can imagine how we teach people to navigate then showing like the sizes, so that people still have a connection with the materiality. I think would be useful. And there also you can talk to someone or book an appointment to have a conversation with a person.. I think that's that digital part, it's how to create a conversation.

INTERVIEW 6 | Anthropologist and Qualitative Researcher, PhD in Anthropology | Colonial politics, social stratification, and research in remote island communities

A: R, it would be so nice to hear about your history and background—just like where you're from, what you studied, where you studied, and what you do right now? Yeah, just generally.

R: I'm a researcher from an erstwhile Dutch colonial territory. I have a background...my bachelor is actually in law, but I did my master in anthropology. I obtained my master's degree in the Southeast Asian Country. And then I continue my PhD here in the Netherland, also anthropology from the University in Amsterdam, and yeah, so last year I did my fellowship at Kai tel...

A: What Institute?

R: Research Institute for...how could I forget. Mostly does research on the Caribbean and Southeast Asia. Part of national academy. It has this collaboration with my research institute in erstwhile Dutch colonial territory—the National Research Agency of erstwhile Dutch colonial territory...So I have that I become the associate researcher for the collaboration for the whole year, from January to December, 2023.

But, yeah, it was only a year. So right now, yeah, I just doing my independent research.

A: Okay, what is your research on right now?

R: Well, my dissertation about the local politics in one of the remote area in eastern erstwhile Dutch colonial territory. So it's like a forgotten island..these are small clusters of islands but despite of their remoteness, the local politics is very dynamic. It's really because they still have this social stratification...which is still a practice there. And then yeah, and then it's intertwined with the electoral politics, and then the history...the colonial heritage is really, still live until now. Yeah, it's still practiced by the people, especially because they, they are still like the noble family and then the.... So when I was doing my field work, I heard about there's also part of the stratification they mentioned about slave, but I couldn't find, at the time, any written document about slavery within the stratification. That's why now I'm kind of interested in that particular subject. Because, yeah, a few months ago I also heard that in the other part of the Island, or the clusters of islands, in other provinces, there is still on social stratification there. There's a label...in erstwhile Dutch colonial territory, we call it Hamba, which is a soft term for a slave or budak, yeah. So, right now I am trying to investigate within the archive.

And then a few months ago, I found the Globalize project, and then they have this archive from the VOC period. And then, yeah, so, yeah, this is my personal interest right now. I really try to, first, of course, understand what, what, in term of this stratification of these people in this island in the eastern part of erstwhile Dutch colonial territory, what it has to do with them, until now, this heritage, and then yeah, and also how the gender relation, the power relation, based on gender caused by this stratification, even though erstwhile Dutch colonial territory, as a state, already have law regarding human rights, like a law regarding the abolishment of slavery. The Dutch colonial still there in erstwhile Dutch colonial territory, they already

abolished slavery, but in practice, yeah, there is still slavery today. So, I really want to know what is the roots for that?

A: Awesome. Tell me one thing, is that the research you're doing now? Or is that the research you did for your PhD?

R: The slavery part...Its what I do now, my personal interest, but I hope I can make it into a project proposal or something, because I also want to do a post doc. I am looking for opportunities.

Well, my dissertation itself is about the contentious politics in the southwestern spice islands region. So, spice islands region., of course, it's part of the history of the spice trade. And then, the spice islands region. at that time, during the European spice trade is really on the northern part. Then they move to center. Then to south eastern part. So, it's an Archipelago province....one of the archipelago province in erstwhile Dutch colonial territory consisting of small islands.

So, after the reformers in erstwhile Dutch colonial territory, when Suharto was, yeah, how can I say it, when the regime change in the 2000 ...also influence of the independence of East Timor. So there are many factors that influence the politics of the localin this particular remote cluster of island.

So, they try to have autonomy. The local islanders of this island, particular southeast part of spice islands region., they want to be to, yeah independent; not from erstwhile Dutch colonial territory, but from their main province, from the center of spice islands region.—from the ambonis, because they think they have different identity and also they've different perspective on the politics, because at that time, the centre of spice islands region. is it's like it's more Dutch influence. But the people from the South East, they are more [inclined] to Republic. So, it was during the period of decolonization of the Dutch from erstwhile Dutch colonial territory. So, it's intertwined since then, the southeastern spice islands region. themselves, they are consisted of many different ethnic group and sub ethnic group in terms of language. In southwestern it's around 25 local language, if we want to talk about language.

But yeah, so after the reformate, the political opportunity was there and also the reform of ...the decentralization... it's create opportunity for these people from the different cluster of island to fight for their autonomy, for their territorial autonomy. So, yeah, my research is about that, and then how... because this a very remote area ... it is really difficult to get there. So I also studied about the diaspora, of the people from there, because in the first movement of their political movement, their diaspora, who lives in the in other provinces in Western part of erstwhile Dutch colonial territory, who have more education, higher education, and then, yeah, they really influence, the trajectory of their political cause.

With the advancement of the internet, and then also more ships go there. And also there's a an Airstream, and then more people come to their island. So the locals had been empowered by the movement itself. So yeah, right now it also intertwined with the social structure. There is this parallel system of local politics, which is created even the colonial period. Of course, there's already changes in the structure because when the Dutch colonial

government established their rule and own government...and then when erstwhile Dutch colonial territory become the independent state, they introduced a new government structure. And then, how this influence also to the local political entity that's already been there for hundreds of years. So, until now, it's very complex. Because not only that are they not aware of their rights as citizens but it affects, especially the people from the lower strata. It's not only fighting for territorial autonomy, but also, it's like mobility, vertical mobility. So yeah, so yeah,

A: And for all this research, did you also engage with archive.

R: No, I did ethnography. I did a multi-sited ethnography, and mostly oral history, because I have to trace years back since when the political movement started? Because when I did my field work, the political actors who started the movement, they are no longer alive. So I try to trace it from the interview, from the oral history of what happened.... First, about the social structure itself, because it's the practice there. And then I also did observation, participant observation... which was, for me, it's really good, because I can really observe how the parallel system is working, Because, I myself, I come from Western part of erstwhile Dutch colonial territory, so I know that the people of this particular village, like, for example, they had this village meeting...it's really different, different from what I have in in capital city, for example. Yeah, they have representation of the clan. And then they still have this rigid system who can talk, who can just sit and then accept the decision...yeah, it's really interesting, because, well, when I did my field work, I position myself as an outsider, of course, because I bring my own background, and then my interpretation of the rights of as a citizen, of erstwhile Dutch colonial territory, and how I compare it, and then how we discuss, and talk about that. Yeah, it's really interesting. I wish I can continue my research.

A: Well, can't you as a post doc?

R: Well, where there is a will, there's a way, hopefully,

A: yeah, I hope so as well.

So I don't know if you had a chance to look at the research proposal, but essentially globalize, wants to go public in one or two years. And so, one of the questions that they're really thinking about is that... because the colonial Archives has a lot of like derogatory terms, very sensitive terminology...we are basically thinking about—particularly for people from former colonies—when they engage with such material, like, what is the experience? And how can we make it a little less distressing? And even if we should, you know? Does that hide some of that violence? So like, I was wondering, if you have some experience? I know you're much more an anthropologist, and therefore use very different methods, but it seems like in your new project, you're moving closer to looking at archives. So, like, if you have experience with engaging with archives, whether that be globalize or any other kind of archive, it would be really nice to hear about that engagement. You know, if you have any, if what it made you feel, you know: were there any barriers to accessing these archives? Of course, language, I know, is already a big one, that's probably, and my guess is, that's why you are learning Dutch, but you know, even, like, institutionally, if you felt some of that, and yeah, like, how we can make that better? So if you have any experience engaging with archives that be very nice to hear about.

L: Well, well, until now, I haven't really engaged with using archive, especially archive like VOC. But in terms of digital archive, when I did my fellowship, they have this project recording The future. It's recording the contemporary situation, and it's employing the observational methods and how camera and then how the interaction from the camera as the extension of the researcher and the people themselves. Well, it's different kind of archive, but yeah, I was involved in the broad production. It will be a different story to share about it.

If we talk about engaging with the colonial archive...my own experience. There's the national archive of erstwhile Dutch colonial territory, but just looking and then sometimes I cannot download it. Yeah, in terms because I don't have access, or I need to contact the key person, the contact person, so, but I read the data first—what is it about? I know about the data first because the recording the future is also using that. With the collaboration of bringing the national research of erstwhile Dutch colonial territory, they provide the platform, yeah,

But, in terms of archive, I have this experience when talking about ancestry rights. One of my informants. He really asked me in erstwhile Dutch colonial territory. He said, Ibu... "Lita? Can you help me find archive about my ancestors? The reason why he asked me to help him find archive about his ancestor— by tracing the family name of their clan—is because he was engaged in the land dispute. So, yeah, it's really sensitive for me, because of the dispute, and also there's this stratification of the people and the power relation between the upper class, the middle and also the lower strata.

But it was also interesting when I have the conversation with the people from the lower stratum. They actually also want to know the written sources, the archive from the VOC, from the Dutch at the time. Because when they told me their ancestor story, their oral history, they want to show me that there's been changes. Because for them, one who should be the leader is from this clan, not that clan, who, who is now sit on the throne like that. So, it's really... and then the impact of who is become the leader...it's also on the access of and property, the land, because the lower strata cannot possess a land. It's always belong to the upper class. So, yeah.

So, in my experience doing my research there, archive is really sensitive, and people from different background will read it, will use it differently.

And for me as a researcher, when we are research on archive, we have this keyword, right how to find the sources...It's also then for me reflecting on that. Because, it's not only the people who needs the archive. So how the label, how to name it, so it's findable....it's easily found by the prospective users. Yeah, I don't know it will, if it helps.

A: No, it's helpful, for sure,

You also told me earlier that for this institution, you were facilitating some sort of interaction between the Dutch and the erstwhile Dutch colonial territory. Yeah, can you tell me a little bit more about that and how do you do that in a way where you know, because there are still existing power relations between the global north and south. So what was it regarding, of course, this collaboration that you were facilitating, and why? You know, because

sometimes, like, we are also thinking about on globalize how to collaborate with local communities, you know, for them to have a say, also on the globalize infrastructure, but like, we are really not me so much, but somebody else on my team is really thinking about how to do that in a way that is not just tokenism, you know. So, since you have some of that experience, it would be nice to hear about that as well. Like, how do you have a fruitful and productive collaboration that also accounts for power relations? You know.

R: Every collaboration of course has its own dynamics and each party has their own goals—they have interests. Of course, the collaborations is meaningful for both parties in terms of expanding network is fruitful for both parties, based on my experience and research. But, there can be friction for example, when one party wants one output, but the other party is not into that. So it's not easy to bridge these different intentions, to mediate different intentions. So, my job to bridge two parties, to make them meet in the middle really is a negotiation and how to negotiate—breaking down the logistics, the prospects—until you reach the goal accepted by the two party. For example, this party wants a publication, but the other one does not want the publication of a scholarly article. We already produced an archive. But the other wants a publication in the international journal. So, yeah, based on my experience to bring two parties onto the table, to negotiate, and work on the scheme, timeframe and the work map.

A: That's really useful, I think, for us as well. I know it's very obvious that it's a constant negotiation, but I had kind of forgotten it. Like for GLOBALISE, the work is not over once we put it out there, but we have to be present to that constant negotiation between the users and the infrastructure for instance. Yeah. That's really a good point, yeah. And then, I was wondering, just like it doesn't have to be related to archives, but you have studied in Southeast Asian Country., you said and then the Netherlands has well. And I was just wondering how your experience has been studying—whether it be colonial history history or not—in both these different, kinds of institutions. What is different about them? Or how perhaps colonial history in particular is taught, discussed, understood—if you can speak to that. And then that you have been thinking about and writing about colonial history, but, the fact that you're doing it also in a Dutch institution, you know, like, is that something that had heart consequences for your research and how you thought about it?

R: Yeah.. It's really different experience, of course, when I did my masters in the Southeast Asian Country. The Southeast Asian Country., of course, had colonial history like erstwhile Dutch colonial territory, while erstwhile Dutch colonial territory, I learn of, I learned the story of the European colonisation—there were Dutch, Portuguese, Spanish. Southeast Asian Country influenced by Spanish. They are majority catholic and the interactions between the people is really different from erstwhile Dutch colonial territory. They like to celebrate together. They have this word Barcada—sitting together, have fun together.

Then I did my PhD here in the Netherlands. I already had a BA in law. The law in erstwhile Dutch colonial territory is really influenced by the Dutch, it is Dutch heritage. In some of that, I wanted to continue studying that here. I also have experience in researching law and society. My thesis is on Muslim, the scripture and national law in erstwhile Dutch colonial territory, so I did legal anthropology in my masters. When I decided to do PhD, yeah, I had to go to Netherland. I kind of hoping that I can, put it together what I already have—combine legal and Anthro perspectives. Amsterdam is a melting pot. Many national nationalities here,

so I enjoy my time here as an anthropologist. It's like doing participant observation every time I go out

So I also did my because I come from erstwhile Dutch colonial territory, but also, I also interact in visual anthropology. produced a documentary about, this endangered language in that remote island in erstwhile Dutch colonial territory. So yeah, I kind of hoping that if I did that fellowship, it's like everything that I already have before my PHd—I continued using that.

A: And you have used the globalize infrastructure a little bit or not?

R: I have. With the topic of Slavery.

A: I'll ask you one last question. I don't know if ever you came across decolonization as a concept. If you have thought about that concept and process, then I would love your thoughts on it to like you know, what can that look like? What does it look like in erstwhile Dutch colonial territory? What can it look like here, particularly for the globalize project? And can be even ever achieved.

R: Decolonisation. In erstwhile Dutch colonial territory it's like different perspective on how to see the period between 1949 and 1950. In erstwhile Dutch colonial territory itself, there's a lot of scholars talking about decolonisation of science. And the relationship between the north and south. My colleagues like to refer to the works of Edward Said—Orientalism. And colleagues accomplished a higher degree in European University, they tried to be critical to themselves. Can we like, based on ground research, it's their own perspective and being from the erstwhile Dutch colonial territory and how we develop science based on the what they train outside erstwhile Dutch colonial territory and how values of erstwhile Dutch colonial territory, and everything. Yeah, and also like there this project about Spice Rout, which yeah, it's like trying to involve more common people—not administratively involved but how they see the history of spice. Lots of activities regarding decolonization in erstwhile Dutch colonial territory.

A: We use it as a sexy term, but I don't know exactly what it will stand for right now. But I think, basically, like I said, right, we want people from various backgrounds to use the infrastructure. It has a lot of problematic terminology, you know, like, for instance, I think when you start doing your research on slaves for instance, I think you will come across a lot of that problematic terminology that which has been used to describe colonised peoples. And I was speaking to somebody from former caribbean colony, who works at the national archives and gives you to access to the reading room and he was like, you know, a lot of researchers, they start crying, you know? And a lot of people, when they look for their family histories they will also come across all that terminology. And that can be very, like, emotionally, like it can really hurt you. And we are thinking of how to do that bit better, right? Do we give a trigger warning, you know? What practices we can put in place that is not as hurtful, but at the same time, I think one doesn't want to hide the violence. So definitely one of the things that globalize is doing, it's contextualizing, giving context of how a term may have been used but at the same time, we want to think of other strategies to make this a safer less triggering experience.

R: I don't know, how GLOBALISE work, but for example, when in searching the description, is there a consultation with the locals—so like not to appropriate the term from the local context. But heres the thing with archives, which is produced years ago, even 100 years ago, but now the term has changed meaning. It's good that Globalise is taking into account user perspective.

A: Second part is—you are a researcher and you know about the globalize infrastructure. But, like, other people like your informants, how are they ever going to discover that even globalize exists?

R: In my experience... I came to Southwestern island, starting in 2011. So, I kind of knew the development of communication technology—how people use mobile phones, when it became popular and the first time someone asked me about how to use Facebook and then through the years because I want to keep connected. So, they are also evolving. The Internet is not really good but it is already there. They know about social media., especially tiktok—they like to dance. They use tiktok, or they also use Zoom, it's really surprising for me. I am also proud of them because they start being connected to the outside world.

Yeah. Now it's the age of technology, of information, communication, and information technology. So, the young people know through popular social media, like Tiktok or Instagram. Soon the other generation, the older one, they will also know. They have discussions on their Facebook group about for example, hey, I know this archive about this.

If Globalise wants to disperse “hey there is this collection of archives here”, the use of social media is really effective right now. But globalize will have to make it more like sexy. Instagrammable. TikTok. Which speaks to that particular generation.

Because I know the past three years of initiation of the youngsters there. The young generation wants to learn about their language, because now the young people don't speak the local language, but speak the national language, that's why that is an endangered language there.. So, communication technology and social media, how to gather people, how to gather diaspora to participate, also to work together on how they can gather words and listing words. It's really interesting. Even people from the remote island know its there.

A: Thank you so much.

R: Thank you for this interesting conversation.